

Music & the Brain

The biophysics and neurobiology of music
and music perception

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“Music is life itself.”- Louis Armstrong

Abstract

How does the brain process music? This is the central research question of our study. The focus of this study is on classical and contemporary Western European music and how the senses, the nervous system and in particular the brain enables people to perceive, produce and above all enjoy music. The common thread, or unifying elements, of our work are the perceptual components or constituents of music such as pitch, rhythm, melody, and harmony, which we have chosen to study from three different perspectives: the origin of music and music theory, the biophysics of music and the ear and the neurobiology of hearing and music perception.

From our central research question, we have derived the following six sub questions, each with its own focus. What is music? What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components of music? What does physics tell us about the perceptual components of music? How does signal transduction in the ear work? How and where are the different perceptual components of music processed in the brain? How do EEG recordings during exposure to a musical stimulus, exposure to ambient noise and while in silent meditation differ and what does this signify?

How the brain processes music can be studied from various perspectives: (evolutionary) genetics, (comparative) anatomy, physiology, computational science, and psychology, each with its own methods and models. Music has been part of the history of man since the earliest beginnings of Homo sapiens, it is found in all cultures present and past as will become clear in the first chapter of this paper. The ability of man to process music and to make music requires many traits, many of these traits have been passed on to us by our predecessors in evolution.

The brain processes music in possibly a predictive manner involving many interconnected pathways and networks, arranged in partly parallel hierarchies, including nuclei in the brain stem and the thalamus, the auditory cortex and other higher cortex areas, and also including the language processing areas Broca's area and Wernicke's area. The different perceptual components or constituents of music, pitch, melody, and harmony are processed partly through different pathways, eventually to be integrated in the auditory cortex. Areas beyond the auditory cortex connect perception with meaning and learning, as well as behavioral or motor reactions to music. The limbic system, somewhat parallel to the perceptual and cognitive processing hierarchies, elicits emotional responses to music.

The processing of music requires attention, externally directed attention required for hearing, internally directed attention required for comprehension and imagination. In this paper we have, among other things, explored the effects of exposure to a musical stimulus or to ambient noise on the (auditive) attention of a test subject, manifested in differences in the relative power of the alpha frequency band of EEG recordings. In a series of experiments, we have found an increase in the in the relative power of the alpha frequency band of a test subject exposed to a musical stimulus compared to a test subject in silent meditation. This is consistent with scientific literature (Schaefer, 2011, Segawa, 2019). We have also found an increase in the relative power of the alpha frequency band of a test subject exposed to ambient noise compared to a test subject in silent meditation. The cafeteria background noise sample used may have been less random than we thought and may have triggered attention or imagination as well. We have found a slight difference in the relative power of the alpha frequency band of test subjects exposed to a musical stimulus compared to a test subject

exposed to ambient noise. The differences found are not statistically significant, due to the relative low number of experiments, but are certainly encouraging.

The study of music and the brain turned out to be a vast area of multidisciplinary science. The study of how the brain processes music has shown to be relevant not only for the understanding of this specific field but also and especially for the whole of neuroscience.

Preface

“Our auditory systems, our nervous systems, are tuned for music. Perhaps we are a musical species as we are a linguistic one.” This quote from Oliver Sacks in “The power of music” (Sacks, 2006) inspired us. We both have opted for a NT/NG profile, and we have a strong interest in the biomedical and natural sciences. In addition, we have both been paying a lot of attention to music for many years. Floris Jan plays trumpet and piano, Kartal piano and bass guitar. We have therefore looked for a subject in which biomedical and natural sciences and music can go together. We were further inspired by “Music, Math and Mind” by David Sulzer (Sulzer, 2021). We have aimed for a cross-domain or cross-subject paper, which has a biology part (“Neurobiology of hearing and music perception”), but also a physics part (“Biophysics of music and the ear”) and an introductory part in music and music theory (“The origin of music and music theory”). We have chosen a broad approach also because at the onset of our study it was still uncertain whether we would be able to make EEG recordings ourselves or not, something we really wanted to do in the biology part of our study it being the only way to make measurements of brain activity ourselves that might be within reach.

How does the brain process music? This is the central research question of our study. From this central research question, we have derived the following six sub questions, each with its own focus. What is music? What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components of music? What does physics tell us about the perceptual components of music? How does signal transduction in the ear work? How and where are the different perceptual components of music processed in the brain? How does the activity in the different frequency bands of an EEG, in particular the alpha frequency band, differ between a test subject exposed to a musical stimulus from a test subject exposed to ambient noise or in silent meditation? We have chosen to let the first four sub questions serve as an introduction or prelude to the latter two, to give our study a clear and also feasible focus on neurobiology. Consequently, we have covered the first four sub questions on an introductory level and covered the latter two sub questions as much in depth as the available means and time allowed.

We started in the summer of 2021 with an online introductory neuroscience course (Mason, 2019), followed by the writing of a short research proposal, including our research questions, how we planned to answer those questions and the general outline for our paper. We then continued with reading up on the subject using introductory level textbooks (Drake, 2019, Luo, 2019, Thaut, 2019, Winterson, 2015), search and selection of scientific literature and with own experimental work. We have attempted to include own experimental and other practical work as much as possible in our study. We have programmed in Python to analyze and visualize sound, we have worked with Sibelius software to generate music score to illustrate music theory concepts, we have studied a microscope slide of the cochlea of a guinea pig, we have dissected a cow’s brain in search for the structures of the auditory pathway, we have further explored the brain online in the Allen Brain Map, we have queried an online fMRI brain image database and finally and most importantly conducted experiments in which we made our own EEG recordings with a consumer market EEG device also used in neuroscience research and analyzed the recordings with open source EEG analysis software.

Embedded within the running text we have included textboxes that either give a brief overview or an in-depth coverage of a specific topic. We have documented all our experimental and other practical work in a separate Lab Notebook.

Floris Jan van Dijk, Kartal van Delden, 2023

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Attachments¹

Lab Notebook
Raw data
Source code

¹ Attachments are separate documents. Raw data published at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7605576>

General introduction

How does the brain process music? This is the central research question of our study. The focus of this study is on classical and contemporary Western European music and how the senses, the nervous system and in particular the brain enables people to perceive, produce and above all enjoy music. The common thread, or unifying elements, of our work are the perceptual components or constituents of music such as pitch, rhythm, melody, and harmony, which we have chosen to study from three different perspectives: the origin of music and music theory, the biophysics of music and the ear and the neurobiology of hearing and music perception.

From our central research question, we have derived the following six sub questions, each with its own focus. What is music? What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components of music? What does physics tell us about the perceptual components of music? How does signal transduction in the ear work? How and where are the different perceptual components of music processed in the brain? How do EEG recordings during exposure to a musical stimulus, exposure to ambient noise and while in silent meditation differ and what does this signify?

We have chosen to let the first four sub questions serve as an introduction or prelude to the latter two, to give our study a clear and also feasible focus on neurobiology. Consequently, we have covered the first four sub questions on an introductory level and covered the latter two sub questions as much in depth as the available means and time allowed.

Music has been part of the history of man since the earliest beginnings of Homo sapiens, it is found in all cultures present and past as will become clear in the first chapter of this paper. The focus of this study is on classical and contemporary Western European music and how the senses, the nervous system and in particular the brain enable people to perceive, produce and above all enjoy music.

Part I

The origin of music and music theory

Chapter 1

What is music?

Introduction

The word 'music' is derived from Ancient Greek μουσική (mousikè), meaning "(art) of the Muses". In classical Greek mythology, the nine Muses were the goddesses who inspired literature, science, and the arts. (Matyszak, 2010) The capacity of humans to discern pitch and tempo patterns may have evolved from pre-existing talents in other animals. (Crespo-Bojorque, 2022) Some of the questions we shall answer in this chapter are: What is music? What is musicality? And how has music developed over time? This chapter attempts to answer these questions from two different perspectives: biology (Beccacece, 2021, Honing, 2018) and music theory (Bernstein, 1973, 1978).

Methods

This chapter is the result of desk research conducted at the start of our study. We started our journey with reading up on the central theme, music and the brain, and next formulating the sub question of this first chapter. We consulted course material (Edwards, 2020) and textbooks (Bernstein, 1978, Sulzer, 2021, Winterson, 2015) to start with, followed by literature search for relevant reviews and primary literature. We used Semantic Scholar[®] and Scite[®] both (free) AI-powered research tools for scientific literature, to search and select relevant literature. To a lesser extent also Google Scholar. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

Results

The origin of music

The origin of music coincides with the origin of man. Music has been part of the history of man since the earliest beginnings of Homo sapiens, it is found in all cultures present and past. The ability of man to process music and to make music requires many traits, many of these traits have been passed on to us by our predecessors in evolution (Crespo-Bojorque, 2022). There are relatively few ancient musical artifacts. The earliest musical instruments known to science are Neanderthal wind musical instruments or flutes discovered in Germany and Slovenia which were used 40.000 years ago. According to cross-cultural study, pitch and rhythm are universal components of music. (Beccacece, 2021)

Definitions of music

Music is a very difficult concept to define. Music is defined differently in different cultures, but it always underlies a kind of global communication and generates an emotional reaction. (Beccacece, 2021). One very simple definition of music is that it is a periodic variation of pitch which combined gives rise to melodies. On the one hand, music can be seen as a universal form of communication, it has a relationship with language, and it is a social and cultural activity (Beccacece, 2021). Music can be defined as a social and cultural construct based on musicality, where there is a distinct difference between music and musicality. Musicality may be described as a set of characteristics that allow for the perception and creation of music. Music then may be viewed as a manifestation of musicality, which differs between cultures and across time (Honing, 2018). On the other hand, music can also be viewed as contributing to mate attraction and reproductive success, parent-infant bonding and thus survival and social bonding in communities (Beccacece, 2021). So, music can be seen as both a cultural product and an evolutionary adaptation.

Music as a cultural product

Music is unique to humanity. It can be seen as a sort of global communication, however it is only somewhat analogous to the vocalizations of other species. (Beccacece, 2021) This may be because the processing of music has many parallels with another unique human trait, namely language.

Other research demonstrates an evolutionary connection between music and language, as both have emotional content, involve the processing of pitch, rhythm, and melody variations, are rule-based, and may be communicated in written form. The intersection of music and language generates two further types of art: song and poetry, both of which contain aspects of both music and language. The involved neural circuitry is not identical, however. (Beccacece, 2021) There are similarities between speech, language, and musicality; some researchers explain these connections by considering musicality to be a linguistic phenomenon. Alternately, musicality may be understood as a natural, spontaneously arising collection of traits that is based on and constrained by cognitive capacities and their underlying biology. This approach holds that musicality is an innate and widely shared musical talent. (Honing, 2018)

Music as an evolutionary adaptation

Why do humans make music? Theories of musical evolution have mostly focused on the importance of music in certain adaptive circumstances such as mate selection, parental care, coalition signaling, and social cohesiveness. Social bonding may be an overarching function that links all of these ideas, and that musicality permitted social bonding at greater scales than grooming and other bonding techniques accessible in primitive communities. Many celebrities in contemporary music are often found attractive by their audiences (Honing, 2018, Savage, 2020).

Humans have musical aptitude, which consists of numerous characteristics such as the capacity to detect pitch and tone length, as well as musical memory. The heterogeneity in this capacity shows that musicality has a hereditary foundation. Genes related with musicality have been identified using genomic techniques (Beccacece, 2021). Comparative research is another effective way for gaining a deeper knowledge of human musical talent and the musical phenotype and evolutionary theories of music and musicality. (Honing, 2018). The multi-component approach is based on the neo-Darwinian premise that if closely related species display comparable solutions to similar challenges, they are most likely employing similar processes. If two related species share a characteristic, it is likely that their common ancestor did as well. If two unrelated species share a trait, this may provide insight into the (potentially distinct) underlying mechanism and the natural selection pressure that may have led to the evolution of that trait. While Charles Darwin suggested that the perception of rhythm was common to all animals, experimental research has only recently begun to support this claim. However, rather than all species having a similar rhythmic ability, there are also aspects of rhythm cognition that appear to be species specific, such as the capability to perceive a regular pulse in a varying rhythm (i.e., one level of a metrical structure) and consequently being able to synchronize to it (i.e., rhythmic entrainment), referred to here as beat-based timing (Honing, 2018). Summarizing, musicality could be an analogue trait, meaning arisen in different species in different locations and converged in a similar direction or a homologue trait, having arisen only once. There is still no final answer to this question.

Much is still unknown about the presumed evolutionary advantage of musical skills and the pressure of natural selection that has kept these traits for many generations since the ice

period. Multiple brain functions, including learning and memory, auditory and visual integration, and complex motor control, are the biological origins of music. (Beccacece, 2021)

Conclusion

Several explanations have been offered regarding the origin and function of music; some research indicates the gradual formation of the talents underlying musicality in primates. Several genes associated with musical talent in humans have been discovered through genomic research, indicating that musical abilities are inherited. Some genes associated with human musicality are likewise associated with animal vocalizations. Current insights about the genetics of musical composition and perception place it in a broader context: music is a sociocultural phenomenon with a biocultural origin and an evolutionary function. (Beccacece, 2021)

Figure 1 Summary of what music is, mind map made with XMind by authors.

The development of Western European music

Music has a long history that can be traced back to prehistory. At first, people would sing in unison with only one voice, but over time men and women began singing in octaves. This is because men and women's voices are naturally an octave apart, which is the first interval of the harmonic series. In the 10th century, the fourth and fifth intervals were added, allowing people to mix intervals of the octave, the fourth, and the fifth, resulting in the sound of multiple simultaneous melodic lines, or polyphony. This was a significant development in the history of music. In the Victorian era, the third interval was added, introducing the concept of the triad and the birth of tonal music. This tonic-dominant relationship was the foundation of a stable tonal language based on the basic notes of the harmonic series. Once this relationship was established, composers began using it extensively, creating a circle of twelve fifths and the twelve different tones of the chromatic scale. These twelve notes of the chromatic scale created a circle of twelve keys that allowed composers to use chromaticism thanks to the "temperate system". However, this chromaticism was kept in check by the diatonic system, which created a stable relationship of tonics, dominants, subdominants, super tonics, new tonics, and new dominants. This system of tonal control was developed and codified by Johann Sebastian Bach, who perfectly balanced the two forces of chromaticism and diatonicism. (Bernstein, 1973, 1978) The relevant parts of music theory will be explained in [Chapter 2](#) - "[What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components of music](#)".

The recent history of Western music is typically divided into four main periods: baroque, classical, romantic, and contemporary. The baroque period, which lasted from 1600 to 1750, is characterized by elaborate and ornate musical styles and the use of complex counterpoint and harmony. Key composers of this period include Bach, Handel, and Vivaldi. The classical period, which lasted from 1730 to 1820, is known for its balance and clarity, with a focus on form and structure. Key composers of this period include Mozart, Beethoven, and Haydn. The romantic period, which lasted from 1815 to 1910, is characterized by emotional and expressive music, with an emphasis on individualism and creativity. Key composers of this period include Chopin, Rachmaninoff, and Tchaikovsky. The contemporary period, which began in the early 20th century, is marked by a wide range of styles and trends, including contemporary classical, jazz, and popular music. Key composers and performers of this period include Shostakovich, Stravinsky, Louis Armstrong, Miles Davis, Duke Ellington, Leonard Bernstein, The Beatles, and the Rolling Stones.

Discussion

There appears to be no single definition of music. It depends on the context and the background of the researchers involved. There is more consensus about the origin and development of music and its place in culture and evolution.

Language research and Chomskyan linguistics

Music could be thought of as a language with a set of sound symbols with a corresponding written notation and grammar-like rules and possibly meaning associated with fundamental chords and melodies. (Philosophy Stack Exchange, 2016) This offers another possibly complementary approach for studying music and the brain.

Chomskyan linguistics offers another perspective on the development of music. Noam Chomsky is an American linguist and cognitive scientist. Chomskyan linguistics is a broad term that refers to the concepts of language and the methodologies of language research developed by Chomsky. Chomskyan linguistics provides a framework to illustrate how music evolved toward greater levels of ambiguity or expressiveness over time, thus dividing music into phonology (the study of sound), syntax (the study of structure) and semantics (the study of meaning). (Wikipedia, 2022)

Chapter 2

What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components of music?

Introduction

What does music theory tell us about the perceptual components or constituents of music, such as rhythm, pitch, melody, and harmony? The selection of music theory concepts discussed and illustrated in this chapter is limited to those concepts that are relevant for this study. This chapter is not a complete introduction to music theory.

Perceptual components of music

Music can be broken down into fundamental components or constituents. In a piece of music, these constituents interact to create a unified whole of a unique cognitive and emotional quality. (Vuust, 2022) In this and next chapters we shall focus on the components rhythm, pitch, melody, and harmony. However, there are many other musical components, such as dynamics, tempo, and form or texture which are beyond the scope of this paper.

Methods

This chapter is partly the result of desk research conducted at the start of our study, as described in the previous chapter. In 2020, one of us (FJ) followed the MOOC Introduction to Music Theory by the University of Edinburgh through Coursera. In this chapter we also made use of the course notes. Additionally, we illustrated some fundamental concepts in music theory or perceptual components of music with Sibelius. Sibelius is a widely used music notation program, named after the Finnish composer Jean Sibelius and originally developed and released by Sibelius Software Limited. In Sibelius one can compose music scores and have Sibelius play a composition back for a variety of musical instruments. For our research we used the free version Sibelius First (Avid, 2021).

Results

Modern musical notation was created by vertically mapping the pitch of musical notes and horizontally mapping the time. The lines and spaces of a staff or stave correspond to eight note scales specified by a key signature, moving up or down by seven lines and spaces indicates an octave or twofold difference in pitch. The amount of time given by the time signature and shape of the note affects the horizontal time axis, with a full note in 4/4 time, for example, showing the length of time as equal to four quarter notes (Sulzer, 2021).

The notes on a staff are used to represent sounds in musical notation. The pitch of a note is determined by its location on the staff, while its duration, or how long it lasts in relation to other notes, is determined by its shape. Silence is represented by rests among other signs. (Winterson, 2014) The next five figures illustrate the different durations notes can have and the relationships between them.

Figure 2 Whole note in 4/4 time signature, empty bars have rests (Illustrations made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Figure 3 Half notes in 4/4 time signature, empty bars have rests (Illustrations made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Figure 4 Quarter notes in 4/4 time signature, empty bars have rests (Illustrations made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Figure 5 Eighth notes in 4/4 time signature, empty bars have rests (Illustrations made by authors with Sibelius Software)

The following figure illustrates the coherence between notes of different length in what is called a rhythm pyramid.

Figure 6 Rhythm Pyramid showing the relationship between whole, half, quarter, eighth and sixteenth notes (Courtesy L. Carpenter)

sharp (#) or a flat (b). An interval is the distance between two notes, measured by the number of notes covered including start and end. When two notes are played simultaneously, they make a harmonic interval. When two notes are played individually, they constitute a melodic interval. The total number of notes found from lowest to highest, including both ends, is used to define intervals. There are two types of (harmonic) intervals in major scales: major intervals (2nd, 3rd, 6th, and 7th) and perfect intervals (4th, 5th and octave). Perfect intervals have a pure sound. The notes of a (harmonic) interval may be sharpened or flattened in either direction, resulting in intervals other than major or perfect (Winterson, 2014).

Figure 8 Bar with treble clef, 4/4 time signature and four quarter notes (Illustration made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Scales

Scales are a collection of related pitches used to produce melody. Scales represent a pathway across an octave. The major and minor scales are the most fundamental scales used in Western music. A scale is a collection of notes organized in ascending or descending order. The major and minor scales are classified as diatonic scales because they are constructed using patterns of seven notes inside an octave. These patterns, which are built on a combination of tones and semitones, give each scale its own sound (Edwards, 2020).

Harmonic scales

Harmonic scales are made up of eight notes in an octave.

Figure 9 Eight notes of the C-major scale (Illustration made by authors with Sibelius Software)

The degrees of the scale

First	Tonic/Keynote	Serves as the focus for the melody and harmony.
Second	Supertonic	
Third	Mediant	Determines tonality of scale, whether major or minor.
Fourth	Subdominant	
Fifth	Dominant	Important for cadential progressions.
Sixth	Submediant	
Seventh	Leading note	It leads your ears back to the tonic.

Tones and semitones

Tones and semitones are measurements for pitch. On a piano a tone is the interval between two white keys separated by a black key – a semitone is the interval between two white keys not separated by a black key. Two semitones make up a tone, between B-C and E-F, there is just one semitone instead of two (Edwards, 2020).

Types of scales

Major scales

Major scales are constructed using the pattern TTSTTTS, where T indicates a whole tone of two semitones and S indicates a single semitone. Additional sharps and flats must be added to preserve this pattern of tones and semitones, as a scale might begin on any note. A major scale generates an open and confident sound that is frequently seen as pleasant by listeners (Edwards, 2020).

Figure 10 G-major scale, the staff features added so called ledger lines to accommodate G, A, B and C (Illustrations made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Figure 11 F-major scale

Minor scales

A minor scale has three distinct variations, each with a unique sequence of intervals but always with a flattened third degree. The variations are the natural, harmonic and melodic minors. The minor third interval adds to the minor keys' distinctive tone. In music, a minor scale creates a sorrowful or even tragic mood (Edwards, 2020).

Chromatic scales

The chromatic scale is made up of all the twelve notes in an octave and is formed of semitones only. It may begin on any note.

Figure 12 Ascending chromatic scale with flats and sharps (Illustration made by authors with Sibelius Software)

There are several other scales in use, a discussion of which is out of scope for this paper.

Key signatures

When a piece of music is built around a specific scale, it is considered to be in that scale's key. To avoid writing the same sharps or flats throughout the work, we assign the piece a certain key. The key of a work indicates which sharps or flats persist throughout the piece. At

the beginning of the staff, we express this by putting the sharps or flats before the time signature. Accidentals are notes that are given additional sharps or flats throughout the composition despite the fact that the key signature does not indicate this (Edwards, 2020).

Melody

Rhythm and pitch together make melody. (Winterson, 2014). Melody is a linear succession of tones which together form a single entity, like a musical sentence. Different melodies can be put together to form musical dialogue, for example question and answer motifs. It also builds a sense of tonality (major, minor, diminished or augmented) through use of intervallic relationships. It can be motivic, for example in film music, a melody is often used to signify a character, time, or place. Melodies can also be conjunct or disjunct, using close or wide intervals and can also be repetitive.

Harmony

Two or more musical lines that sound in unison create harmony; harmony can be interpreted as consonant or dissonant (Winterson, 2014). Harmony is a term that refers to the effect of intervals and chords, as well as their interrelation (Edwards, 2020). Its basic principle is consonance versus dissonance, which is entirely based on perception, opinion, and familiarity. This relationship gives harmonic movement a forward momentum building narrative and interest.

Consonance and Dissonance

Consonant and dissonant intervals are both harmonic intervals. Consonance and dissonance are musical terms that refer to the sensations of stability and repose (consonance) versus tension or conflict (dissonance) experienced by a listener when particular tonal or note combinations are played simultaneously.

Figure 13 Minor second interval and perfect fifth interval (Illustration made by authors with Sibelius Software)

Is there an inbuilt preference for consonance in man? Numerous research has been undertaken to determine if consonance is an intrinsic preference, however the results indicate otherwise. According to recent study, there was no compelling preference for consonance. This study also discovered a correlation between harmonic preference and years spent playing a musical instrument, implying that musical exposure boosts preferences for harmonic frequencies due to their musical importance (McDermott, 2010). Different people may experience the same musical material differently due to different frames of reference (Vuust, 2022), this will be further explained in Chapter 5 “How is music processed in the brain” of this paper.

Chord

A chord is the sounding of two or more notes simultaneously, resulting in harmony. The triad is the fundamental building block of harmony, it is a chord composed of three notes.

Cadences

In music, a cadence is the moment at which the melody finishes, and the piece of music seems completed or closed or incomplete. Imperfect or Half Cadence refers to a cadence that feels incomplete and lingers around the dominant chord until the music decides to go on. A Perfect Cadence is a cadence that feels completed or closed and so travels from the dominant chord back to the tonic (Edwards, 2020).

Tuning

Tuning and temperament are musical concepts that refer to the process of adjusting a single sound source, such as a voice or string, to provide a desired pitch proportional to a given pitch, as well as the process of altering that tuning to eliminate dissonance. There are several tuning techniques.

The earliest kinds of tuning date all the way back to ancient times. Pythagoras of Samos (570–495 BC), sometimes referred to as the "Father of Music and Mathematics," created what is known as "Pythagorean Tuning." The frequency ratios of all intervals in this tuning scheme are based on the 3:2 ratio of the "pure" perfect fifth interval. The "Circle of Fifths" discussed in a separate textbox is therefore also called the "Pythagorean circle".

Another method of tuning is referred to as "Equal Temperament." This tuning style is frequently attributed to two individuals: Zhu Zaiyu (1536-1611 AD) and Simon Stevin (1548-1620 AD). Equal temperament entails the ability to split an octave (or any other interval) into equal steps. This results in the division of an octave into 12 equal sections. As a result, in 12-tone equal temperament, the chromatic scale covers all 12 of the available pitches. This remains the most widely used tuning system in the Western world to this day.

Conclusion

In this chapter we have tried to simplify relevant parts of music theory and create a simple frame of reference for the reader of this paper. Music theory is an enormous field of study on its own. This chapter only covers some essentials of music theory that we think are relevant for the next chapters this paper: rhythm, pitch, melody, and harmony.

Discussion

It was at first hard to determine what in music theory is relevant for this study. We let ourselves be guided by selected scientific publications (Honing, 2019, Sulzer, 2021) published on the neuroscience of music.

The Circle of Fifths

The circle of fifths is a way of visualizing the relationship between the twelve chromatic musical keys. It is called the circle of fifths because each key is arranged a fifth interval away from the next on the circle, creating a clockwise sequence of perfect fifths. An interval is the distance between two notes, measured by the number of notes covered including start and beginning. The primary triads of any key can simply be found by looking at either side of the keynote or tonic. A triad is a chord made up of three notes. A chord is the simultaneous sounding of two or more notes producing harmony. Harmony can be consonant or dissonant. (Winterson, 2014) The Circle of Fifths shows each key with its key signature. The practical use of the Circle of Fifths is exemplified in the piece "Giant Steps" by John Coltrane (1960), where Coltrane walks through the different keys of the Circle of Fifths in specific sequences. Listen to "[Giant Steps](#)" for free on Spotify.

Figure 14 Circle of Fifths (Wikimedia Commons)

In the scale, the tonic and dominant have a strong relationship. Due to the fact that each scale has its own dominant (5th degree), you may take fifths of fifths of fifths, with each note yielding a new tonic with a new dominant. This results in a complete circle of notes. This is referred to as the circle of fifths. (Bernstein, 1973, 1976)

Part II
The biophysics of music and the ear

Chapter 3

What does physics tell us about the perceptual components of music?

Introduction

Physics discuss matter and energy, and the relations between them and other phenomena. It can explain almost every possible phenomenon and with that information predict the outcome of events. Sounds can be understood by segregating them into multiple components: frequency (pitch), amplitude, timbre, envelope, velocity, wavelength and phase. By using these components of sound, the physics behind music can be understood. All these concepts are construed in this chapter. Many of the components of sound are discussed in musical terms in [Chapter 2: What does music tell us about the perceptual components of music?](#) In the explanations below, only the physics are discussed.

Methods

This chapter is the result of desk research conducted at the start of our study. The basics of sounds in physics and the corresponding mathematical knowledge were learnt through education at school.

Results

Sounds are described as waves in physics, which have their own properties. The way that humans perceive sound and their capability of distinguishing different sounds, is dependent on how these properties of various sounds differ. These distinct features of waves make up the components of sounds.

Vibrations

If a wave repeats itself, a vibration is created, which sounds like a constant tune. There are two types of vibrations: lateral vibrations and longitudinal vibrations. Lateral vibrations move up and down, like a rope or a beach wave. Longitudinal vibrations travel sideways by pushing themselves. All sounds are longitudinal vibrations that travel through matter. A longitudinal vibration can be easily described by using the particle model. When a particle in space pushes against another, the other particle in its turn pushes against the next, and this starts a chain reaction of particles bumping into each other. Due to this, areas in space are created with relatively low and relatively high densities, which can be described as waves, making a vibration. The easiest way to display a longitudinal wave, however, is to display it as a lateral wave, which is much more uncluttered and therefore easier to read.

Components of sound

Frequency

The frequency, or pitch, of a sound is in correlation with the number of times a wave repeats itself in one second. This is the inverse of the vibration time, that is to say the time per single wave. It is therefore described as one over the vibration time: $f = \frac{1}{T}$ with T being the vibration time. The higher the frequency, the more frequent a wave repeats, the higher the pitch. The unit for frequency is Hertz (Hz).

Amplitude

The amplitude is the deviation (height or depth) of a wave. The amplitude causes the increase or decrease of the volume of a sound. The higher the amplitude, the higher the wave, the louder the sound. It is measured in decibels (dB)

Timbre

The central C on the piano sounds different from the C on the guitar, even though their frequencies are the same. This is due to the timbre, which is the result of primarily the envelope (defined below), and the fundamental frequency and their overtones (explained under *Frequencies in scales*). Every note played on an instrument is the result of multiple waves creating one intricate wave containing multiple frequencies. When the note sounds distinct in its frequency, it is composed of a fundamental frequency and its overtones, for example notes on a flute. The snare on a drum set, on the other hand, does not seem to have a clear note and therefore consists of many more frequencies than the note on a flute, many of which are not multiples of one fundamental frequency.

Envelope

The envelope of a sound consists in itself of four different concepts: the attack, the decay, the sustain, and the release. These in turn describe different parts of how a sound changes over time. The attack is the time it takes for a tone to reach its peak amplitude after its initiation. The decay is the time it takes for the tone to drop to the sustain level from its peak. The sustain is the amplitude of the tune when it has stabilized. Lastly, the release is the time for the amplitude on the sustain level to drop to zero.

Velocity

The velocity of a sound is how fast the sound travels through space. This is influenced by temperature and differs in various states of matter.

Wavelength

The wavelength of a wave is the length of a single wave, designated by λ (lambda). The wavelength is dependent on the frequency: if the frequency is higher, the wavelength is shorter, and on the speed of the sound: if the speed of sound is higher, the wavelength is shorter. The formula for wavelength is therefore: $\lambda = \frac{c}{f}$ or $\lambda = c \cdot T$ with $f = \frac{1}{T}$ and c being the speed of sound. Because the wavelength is dependent on the speed of sound, it is dependent on the state of matter in which the wave travels.

Phase

The phase of a wave refers to the stage in which the wave is. This is relevant, because two waves with opposite phases cancel each other out, lowering the amplitude, while waves with the same phase strengthen each other, causing an increase in amplitude. This is because the low-pressure areas that the wave causes are compensated by the high-pressure areas from the wave with a phase opposite from the initial wave. It is notated as φ (phi) representing angle, since a wave is a circle, but since the phase difference is more relevant it is often notated as the function of the time: $\varphi(t) = 2\pi \frac{t-t_0}{T}$ with t_0 being the starting time, and T being as usual the vibration time.

Music explained with physics

Frequencies in scales

As explained in chapter 2, the most basic modern scales are the major scale and the minor scale, both consisting of eight notes (seven if you do not count the last note, which is a repetition of the first note, but one octave higher). Every scale has a fundamental note, which is most often the note that is played first and last in order from low to high frequency, meaning, in musical theory terms, from low in the alphabet to high in the alphabet and therefore the note that is repeated. The fundamental note carries a frequency, which is called the fundamental frequency, or f_0 . The rest of the notes are determined by specific multiples of the fundamental frequency. These are presented in the table below taking the A major scale as an example and starting at the central A4.

	f_0	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_4	f_5	f_6	f_7
Note	A	B	C#	D	E	F#	G#	A
Frequency (Hz)	440	495	550	586	660	743	825	880
Multiple of f_0	1	9/8	5/4	4/3	3/2	27/16	15/8	2/1

Figure 15 Table of fundamental frequency multiples in A major and their respective frequencies.

Most notable in the table is that multiplying a tone's frequency results in the same tone, though one octave higher. Taking a frequency and multiplying it with a power of two, gives the same sound, but with a higher pitch. This can be explained by the fact that a wave with power of two smaller wavelength ($\lambda = \frac{c}{f}$ so, if the frequency doubles, the wavelength halves) has overlapping phases given they begin in the same phase, or half the phase or double the phase of the other.

Also relevant are the multiples belonging to f_3 and f_4 , the fourth and fifth notes in the scale. These are, as mentioned in chapter 2, called perfect intervals. They are the most important notes in a scale, which can be seen in, for example, twelve-bar blues. Those cord structures follow: $f_0f_0f_0f_0$, $f_3f_3f_0f_0$, $f_4f_3f_0f_0$. Their multiples of the fundamental frequency are also the simplest fractions, which could be an explanation for their often-used harmony with the fundamental frequency.

Instrumentation

The difference in use of instruments gives texture to a song and dictates the mood of the song.

Rhythm

Rhythm can be described as the consistent repetition of sound, regularly short sounds, meaning short vibrations. Difference in rhythm means difference in the relation between silence and sound of a song. Because rhythm is consistent, rhythm can be seen as a vibration itself.

Analysis of sample audio recordings

What does physics teach us about the perceptual components of music? A musical note played on different musical instruments has different compositions of a base or fundamental frequency and its harmonics, depending on the instrument. We have adapted selected open-source computer code in Python for our purposes and used it for the spectral analysis of sample audio recordings of an A4 played on different musical instruments. Selected results are shown by the graphs below. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

Figure 16 Spectrograms of A4 on Bb trumpet and piano respectively.

The spectrograms show the base frequency A4 or 440 Hz as well as the same multiples of the base frequency or harmonics, however the power distribution of the base frequency and harmonics differs from one instrument to another accounting for the timbre characteristic for each instrument. Our Lab Notebook (Attachment) also includes the spectral analyses of an A4 played on a C-Trumpet and a Flugelhorn. A C-Trumpet is a trumpet tuned in the key of C, instead of Bb, refer to Chapter 2 for music theory. A flugelhorn is another trumpet-like brass instrument with a wider bore and more mellow sound and tuned in the key of Bb.

Figure 17 From top to bottom: Flugelhorn, Bb Trumpet, C Trumpet (photograph by authors)

Simulation of perceptual components

What does physics teach us about the perceptual components or constituents of music? We have adapted selected open-source computer code in Python to visualize some music theory concepts from a physics perspective. Selected results are shown by the graphs below. Our [Lab notebook](#) (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

Harmonics

Figure 18 A4 at 440 Hz as fundamental frequency and its first and second harmonics at two and three times the fundamental frequency respectively.

Consonance

Figure 19 C4 and a C5 and their sum being also a perfect harmonic wave, the latter being perceived as consonance.

Our Lab notebook (Attachment) also includes visualizations of examples of imperfect consonance and dissonance.

Conclusion

Music can be described and manipulated using classical physics through the understanding of waves and vibrations. The properties of the waves that make up the vibrations determine the perception of sound, and since music is sound it can therefore be described using the mathematics applicable to vibrations. Doing this enlightens us as to why some tunes sound right and others sound wrong and guides us to a definition of music supported by science.

Cross-domain research and physics

The analysis of music from a physics perspective is complementary to the analysis of music from a music theory perspective, thus connecting the domains of the arts and the natural sciences.

Discussion

Though it is not yet possible to define music, it is made up of different vibrations that can be split into singular sinusoids, meaning the sound of music can be defined.

Fourier analysis

The spectral analyses of the sample audio recordings were done with a standard function for Fourier analysis of the Python SciPy package. With Fourier analysis a musical signal or any other periodic signal can be analyzed into its individual frequency components. (Lenssen, 2014) The corresponding textbox in our [Lab notebook](#) (Attachment) gives a further explanation of Fourier analysis.

Chapter 4

How does signal transduction in the ear work?

Introduction

To define music, we need to take a closer look at how sounds are processed in the ear, for these determine the parameters of how music is perceived. From the previous chapter we know that frequency is manifested as pitch in our ears, that amplitude is manifested as intensity, and that envelope and arrangements of sundry frequencies are manifested as timbre. This chapter will cover how these parameters are processed in the ear, and how this influences our musical perception.

Anatomy - Overview

The following anatomic parts of the ear are relevant for this paper:

- Auricle
- Tympanic membrane
- Ossicles
- Cochlea
- Organ of Corti, spiral organ

Figure 20 Transmission of sound in the middle and inner ear (Drake, 2019)

The structure and function of the ear are further discussed in the running text of this chapter. The Organ of Corti and signal transduction will be further discussed more in depth in separate text boxes.

Methods

The information presented in this chapter was gathered by further educating ourselves regarding the biology and physiology of the ear through the reading of books and papers. This was done by consulting the work of David Sulzer, who often refers to Lisa Olson, and articles covering the biology and physiology of the ear by Geoffrey A. Manley.

Physiology - Overview

The human audibility has an incredible range of 1 to 10^{12} dB, with 1 dB being the smallest change the ear can detect. The human ear can detect sounds within the 20 Hz to 20 kHz frequency range. The following subsequent processes occur in the ear:

- Reception
- Transmission
- Transduction

These processes are further discussed in the running text of this chapter. Signal transduction will be elaborated upon more in-depth in separate text boxes.

Results

The ear consists mainly of three regions: the outer ear, the middle ear and the inner ear, which each their own parts in translating soundwaves to electrical signals.

Figure 21 The human ear.

The outer ear

The outer ear itself consists of three parts: the external ear, which is the part of the ear visible from just looking at someone, the ear canal, and the ear drum. The outer ear funnels sound waves to the ear canal, greatly increasing the amplitude by concentrating the sounds in a more confined space which increases the pressure-contrast in the longitudinal waves which sound consists of. The funneling of sound waves is possible due to the pinna, which is the collective term for the folds in the ear that direct sound waves to the ear canal. The sound

waves, after travelling through the entire ear canal, then reach the tympanic membrane, better known as the ear drum, which is remarkably similar to a drumhead. It is made up of thin skin, mucosal and laminar layers. The tympanic membrane transduces airwaves into mechanical vibrations, of which the energy is passed down to the bones of the middle ear.

The middle ear

The middle ear features the three smallest bones of the human body: the hammer, the anvil and the stirrup, collectively known as the ossicles. The tympanic membrane transfers the energy from the mechanical vibrations created from the sound waves to the malleus (hammer), which strikes the incus (anvil). The incus in its turn transfers the energy from the mechanical waves given to it from the malleus to the stapes (stirrup). The stapes, like a piston, pushes the oval window at the entrance of the inner ear, finally transmitting the mechanical vibrations to the inner ear. To the stapes connected is the stapedius reflex, which stabilizes the stapes often in response to loud sounds, pulling the stapes back from the oval window, which decreases the transmission of energy to the inner ear. It is also the smallest skeletal muscle in the human body with its 1 mm in length (Sulzer, 2021). The frequency at which the malleus strikes the incus is equal to the frequency of the sound waves which the tympanic membrane transduces to mechanical vibrations. Therefore, the rate at which the stapes pushes against the oval window of the inner ear is equal to the frequency of the sound waves, because the frequency of the malleus striking the incus is equal to the frequency of the incus transmitting its mechanical energy to the stapes. Though the extensive transferring of energy could seem to prompt high rates of faults, the efficiency of transmitting energy to the inner ear is about 50%, which is surprisingly high (Olson, 2021).

Eustachian Tube

The Eustachian tube connects the nasopharynx, a cavity behind the ear and above the throat, to the middle ear, mediating the air pressure in the middle ear. This is necessary since the middle ear is not connected to the atmosphere due to the tympanic membrane blocking the pathway. This can be problematic, because a large enough contrast in air pressure between the atmosphere and the middle ear could cause damage to the eardrum. To control the pressure in the middle ear, the Eustachian tube allows air from the nasopharynx to reach the middle ear changing the air pressure in the middle ear to correspond to the air pressure in the nasopharynx, which has the same air pressure as the atmosphere in which one is situated. The Eustachian tube is normally closed but opens when muscles contract during actions like chewing or by forcefully blowing wind inside the tube, an action performed by divers by closing the nose and then blowing into it.

Figure 22 Eustachian tube

The inner ear

The inner ear, as appose to the outer ear which is filled with air, is filled with fluids called endolymph and perilymph, on which the mechanical vibrations are passed down by the moving oval window which is controlled by the stapes. It contains the cochlea and various nerves, tubes and canals connected to the cochlea. The cochlea itself resembles a snail and consist of an outer spiral and an inner coil. Attached to the cochlea are the semicircular canals, which are not relevant to hearing but rather to one's sense of balance. Together, the semicircular canals and the cochlea form the membranous labyrinth. Three chambers divide the tissue within the cochlea: the scala vestibuli, the scala media and the scala tympani, which are separated by two membranes in total. The scala vestibuli and the scala media are separated by the Reissner's membrane, and the scala media and the scala tympani are separated by the basilar membrane and a layer of cells called the organ of Corti, which features hair cells that sends information to the brain through nerves. A third membrane sits atop the organ of Corti, called the tectorial membrane finding its relevance in outer hair cell operation. These hair cells separate sound into its many frequencies to be converted into electrical and chemical signals.

Cochlea and Organ of Corti – Part I

The word cochlea comes from the Greek word for snail (“Κοχλίας”) because of its snail shell like shape. The cochlea is part of the inner ear, which is entirely contained within the temporal bone of the skull in a cavity called the bony labyrinth. The ossicles of the middle ear amplify and transmit sound waves received by the outer ear and pass the amplified sound waves on to the membrane of the oval window of the cochlea. Starting at the oval window the sound waves propagate through the perilymph of the scala vestibuli up to the apex of the cochlea, from there the sound waves continue through the perilymph of the scala tympani away from the apex towards the round window membrane. The sound waves also travel through the basilar membrane, the membrane that separates the scala tympani from the cochlear duct or scala media. In the cochlear duct on the basilar membrane rests the organ of Corti or spiral organ. The organ of Corti harbors sensory cells - cells with cilia or hair cells - that transduce the mechanical stimuli of the movement of the basilar membrane into electrical stimuli. The activated sensory cells release neurotransmitters that elicit action potentials in underlying neurons of the spiral ganglion, the action potentials travel through the afferent fibers that make up most of the vestibulocochlear nerve or auditory nerve to the brain (Gommers, 2020, Luo, 2019).

Figure 23 Cochlea, transverse section, schematic drawing (Drake, 2019)

Figure 24 Cochlea, cross-section, schematic drawing (Wikimedia)

Cochlea and Organ of Corti – Part II

Amazing images of the cochlea. The first image shows a 3D micro CT-scan of a human cochlea “colored” with Osmium a metal, showing nerve fibers emerging from the spiral ganglion. The second image shows a light micrograph of a human cochlea labeled with immunohistochemistry, showing hair cells labeled in red, neuronal fibers labeled in green and cell nuclei labeled in blue.

Figure 25 3D CT-scan of human cochlea (Boogert, 2018)

Figure 26 Light micrograph of human cochlea labelled with immunohistochemistry (Pouyo, 2018)

Organ of Corti of guinea pig

Figure 27 Photograph of cross-section of the organ of Corti of a guinea pig showing outer hair cells, inner hair cells and neurons of the cochlear nerve, cell nuclei are labeled in blue, magnification approximately 2,500 times. (Photograph by authors)

Signal transduction - Overview

The transduction of sound to action potentials in the ear can be divided into two sequences: the mechanical transmission of kinetic energy and then the transduction of kinetic energy to electrical energy:

1. sound waves → tympanic membrane → malleus → incus → stapes → oval window → vestibular canal → basilar membrane →
2. stereocilia of hair cells (inner, outer) → potassium ion flux → calcium ion flux → neurotransmitter release → action potentials cochlear nerve

The three aspects of the signal transduction of sound are the physical grounding of the cognitive attributes of sound.

Physical attributes	Coding	Cognitive attributes
Quantity/Length (s)	Spike train/Length (s)	Duration
Frequency (Hz)	Location/Tonotopic	Pitch
Intensity/Amplitude (dB)	Rate of firing (Hz)	Loudness

The duration or length (s) of a sound is coded as the length (s) of the sequence of action potentials or spike train. The frequency (Hz) of a sound is coded as the specific location on the organ of Corti or spiral organ of the hair cells that release neurotransmitter in response to a specific frequency. This is called tonotopic mapping. Tonotopic mapping is further explained in a separate textbox. The loudness (dB) or amplitude of a sound is coded as the frequency (Hz) or firing rate of the sequence of action potentials or spike train (Howard, 2019).

Tonotonic mapping

Sound frequencies are represented as a tonotopic map in the cochlea. The basilar membrane is a resonant structure with physical properties - flexibility, mass, and width - that are graded along its length. The physical properties of the basilar membrane at a given point along its length determine its characteristic frequency, the frequency at which it resonates with another frequency. One effect of this is the separation of a sound wave into its component frequencies along the length of the basilar membrane. Another is the activation of sensory cells or hair cells in the organ of Corti at frequency specific locations along its length. This is called tonotopic mapping. The basilar membrane is widest and most flexible at the apex of the cochlea, and narrowest and least flexible at the base. This makes that the sensing of high-frequency sounds is localized near the base of the cochlea, while sensing of low-frequency sounds is localized near the apex (Luo 2019, p.245-246). The brain also uses mapping to organize information. Sound frequencies are represented as a tonotopic map in the auditory cortex (Ciesla, 2020), this will be further explained in [Chapter 5 - "How is music processed in the brain"](#) of this paper.

The mechanotransduction by the hair cells, of which there are around 15,500 in the cochlea, is performed using the stereocilia, which are the hairs of the hair cells (Sulzer, 2021). An individual hair cell contains 20 to 300 stereocilia arranged in bundles, with in the middle the tallest hairs and on the rims the shortest hairs. Though hair cells have synapses they are not considered neurons due to their lack of axons and dendrites and inability to fire action potentials. They are therefore classified as epithelial cells. The longer stereocilia of the outer hair cells attach to the tectorial membrane. Hair cells respond to mechanical movements and transduce those to electrical signals by opening ion channels. Motion-sensitive stereocilia ion channels are opened by the mechanical force that is produced when the stereocilia are brought into vibration by the basilar membrane. The stereocilia ion channels cause potassium to enter the hair cells causing their depolarization. The depolarization causes the activation of calcium channels, which then results in the release of glutamine, a neurotransmitter, effectively conveying information to the brain as electrical signals through the auditory nerve and completing the translation from auditory waves to electrical signals.

Outer hair cells

Motor properties of outer hair cells amplify auditory signals and sharpen frequency tuning. There are two amplification mechanisms that cause positive feedback. A mechanical stimulus leads to hair bundle deflection, which leads to mechanosensitive ion channel opening, which leads to depolarization and through hair bundle motility to further hair bundle deflection. A mechanical stimulus also leads to hair bundle deflection, which leads to mechanosensitive ion channel opening, which leads to depolarization, which leads to electromotility of the hair cell shortening it and further displacing the tectorial membrane. This electromotility is a unique property of outer hair cells, mediated by the protein prestin. Outer hair cells are innervated mostly by efferent fibers of the vestibulocochlear nerve or auditory nerve from the brain, through which the brain controls the level of sensitivity of the outer hair cells (Luo, 2019).

Inner hair cells

In the cochlea sounds are converted into electrical signals by mechanically gated ion channels in the stereocilia of inner hair cells. Each inner hair cell extends a bundle of hairs or stereocilia from its apical surface. Each stereocilium is a rigid cylinder, rich in actin fibers, with a constriction at its base that enables it to pivot. The stereocilia of a single inner hair cell are arranged in rows of increasing height. The apical end of a stereocilium is connected to its taller neighbor by a structure called the tip link. Sound wave induced relative movements between neighboring stereocilia causes the tip link to open mechanosensitive ion channels. This causes K^+ influx and depolarization of the hair cell. In turn this opens voltage gated Ca^{2+} ion channels leading to Ca^{2+} influx and release of the neurotransmitter glutamate, leading to depolarization of peripheral endings of spiral ganglion neurons (Luo, 2019).

Figure 28 Mechanoelectrical transduction in hair cells, image made in BioRender®.

Conclusion

The transduction of sound waves to electrical signals requires a network consisting of the smallest bones in the body to the most sensitive of nerves to process the through physics acquired information with the highest precision. Sound waves are first amplified in the outer ear, to be then converted into mechanical waves through the tympanic membrane. Passed on by the hammer, anvil, and stirrup, the mechanical waves get transferred by the oval window to a fluid that gets picked up by hairs in the cochlea to then be send as electrical signals to the brain.

Discussion

While the ear works more complicated than described in this chapter, the parts necessary for understanding the transferring of information regarding wave properties give a good feel for how things work in the ear.

Audiogram

The image below shows a so-called audiogram, with the typical frequency ranges and intensity ranges of some in the context of music common sources of sound, and hearing thresholds in blue and red. Presbycusis is age-related hearing loss, which manifests itself mostly in the higher frequency ranges.

Figure 29 Audiogram (Adapted from Mason, 2019)

Part III

The neurobiology of hearing and music perception

Chapter 5

How and where is music processed in the brain?

Introduction

How and where are the different perceptual components or constituents of music processed in the brain? In order to be able answer this question, this chapter first explores the anatomy and physiology of the human brain, models of music processing and brain imaging technology used in brain research.

Methods

Literature

We consulted textbooks (Drake, 2020, Luo, 2019), course material from the MOOC Understanding the Brain by the University of Chicago through Coursera (Mason, 2019), an earlier paper (Dijk, F.J. van, 2017) and primary literature (Honing, 2018, Koelsch, 2011, Reybrouck, 2021, Scherder, 2017, Vuust, 2014, Vuust, 2022, Warren, 2008). Additionally, we used the Allen Brain Atlas from the Allen Institute for Brain Research, set up by Paul Allen, co-founder of Microsoft, to further our understanding of the anatomy of the brain. (Allen Institute for Brain Science, 2022) Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a lab report of this practical work.

Dissection

We dissected a mammal brain ourselves to see if we could locate some of the structures of the auditory pathway. We first reviewed a recorded dissection of the auditory pathway in the human brain (Mason, 2019). Secondly, we attempted a dissection of a pig's brain because cow's brain was not available due to bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) risk. The average weight of a pig's brain is only 250 g as compared to an average of 1,400 g for a human brain. In particular the telencephalon is smaller, not only in absolute terms but also and especially relative to its overall size. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work. Eventually, school helped out in providing a cow's brain. We did a successful dissection of the cow's brain. We located the vestibulocochlear nerves, but other structures of the auditory pathway proved not visible. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

Models

We have given the development of comprehensive models in research of how the brain processes music a lot of attention. We have compared and contrasted functional, cognitive, and probabilistic models.

Imaging

We also read up on two relevant technologies for brain imaging fMRI and EEG, both used in research on music and the brain. They are both way beyond the resources available for this study, or so we thought. We have used a fMRI database (Neurosynth, 2022) holding fMRI images from thousands of studies, which can be searched on a research topic for example music and the search result can be navigated showing brain activity when listening to music. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

Finally, we have purchased and successfully used in experiments a modest EEG device (Muse2™) and open-source EEG analysis software (EEGLAB) for this study, this is further

reported on in Chapter 6 of this paper. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a lab report of this practical work as well.

Results

Anatomy

To get a good understanding of the functioning or physiology of the human brain and how it processes e.g. music, it is necessary to get a good understanding of its anatomy. To get a good understanding of the anatomy of the human brain, it is necessary to first review the early development or ontogeny of the brain briefly in the human embryo. Approximately two weeks after fertilization a tube-like structure is formed in the outer layer of cells or ectoderm of the embryo called the neural tube. The neural tube will develop into the central nervous system and part of the peripheral nervous system. At the anterior end of the neural tube three vesicles are formed, commonly indicated as hindbrain, midbrain and forebrain, the forebrain is then further divided into telencephalon and diencephalon resulting in a four-vesicle structure. After approximately three weeks after fertilization two optic vesicles are formed from the diencephalon which will develop into eyes. This four plus two vesicle pattern remains the basic structure in the further development of the human brain. The hindbrain will further develop into the cerebellum and the brainstem up until the pons. The telencephalon vesicles will further develop into hemispheres of neural tissue, folding itself over, like a ram's horn, in humans forming the larger part of the brain. (Mason, 2019)

Figure 30 The development of the ventricular system. The dorsal views (A–C) correlate with the lateral views (D–F) at 5 weeks (D), 6 weeks (E), and 8.5 weeks (E, F) of gestation respectively. The dashed lines outline the ventricles. (Drake, 2020)

This early embryonic development or ontogeny of the human to some extent also reflects the evolutionary development or phylogeny of the brain in the animal kingdom, where the anatomy of the brain varies from a simple tube-like structure in e.g. annelids to a human like anatomy of the brain in (other) primates (Mason, 2019).

We are born with a surplus of neurons. Typically, by the age of eight years, our brains undergo a major make over, pruning any neurons that are not needed. This is why it is relatively easy to learn a language or music at an early age. Your brain becomes wired for music if you learn music as a child. Studies on the anatomical and physiological levels have revealed that musical training has a variety of structural and functional impacts on the brain. (Beccacece, 2021) A trained musician, for instance, processes music somewhat differently compared to non-musicians. Other studies have demonstrated that both listening to and performing music cause epigenetic modifications and changes in the expression of numerous genes at the molecular level. (Beccacece, 2021, Kanduri, 2015) These genetic changes lie at the basis of the structural and functional impact of music on the brain.

The human ear only has 3,500 inner hair cells, which is few compared to the more than 100 million photoreceptors of the human eye. Still the human ear and brain together are well adapted to the perception of music (Sugaya, 2019).

The central nervous system is composed of grey matter and white matter. The cell bodies of the neurons and supporting cells make up the grey matter, while the myelinated axons with other supporting cells make up the white matter. In the brain, the surface, or cortex, and the nuclei consist of grey matter with white matter on the inside. In the spinal cord this distribution is vice versa.

The following three images show the overall anatomy of the human brain, with the names of the main areas and structures.

Figure 31 Left lateral view (Drake, 2020)

Figure 32 Sagittal section (Drake 2020)

Figure 33 Cranial nerves (Drake 2020)

The following images are screenshots from an online dissection of the human brain, part of the MOOC “Understanding the Brain – The Neurobiology of Everyday Life” by The University of Chicago via Coursera® (Mason, 2019).

Figure 34 Human brain in situ with bone and outer meninges removed, superior view (Mason, 2019)

Figure 35 Human brain, still covered in the arachnoid mater, lateral view (Mason, 2019)

Figure 36 Human brain, midsagittal cut, overview (Mason, 2019)

Figure 37 Human brain, midsagittal cut, details, annotation by authors (Mason, 2019)

Figure 38 Human brain, inferior view, metal probe pointing at vestibulocochlear nerve (Mason, 2019)

The following two images are from our dissection of a cow's brain. The brain had suffered somewhat in the slaughterhouse and from subsequent freezing and thawing.

Figure 39 Cow's brain, lateral view (Photograph by authors)

Figure 40 Dissection probe pointing at cranial nerve possibly vestibulocochlear nerve at medulla and pons (Photograph by authors)

Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a full lab report of this practical work.

The following drawing gives a flat schematic of the human brain, showing all major structures.

*Figure 40 Human brain, a flat schematic (Mason, 2019). **F**rontal, **P**arietal, **T**emporal, **O**ccipital*

Auditory pathway

Auditory signals from the auditory or cochlear nerve are processed by multiple brainstem nuclei before reaching the thalamus and the auditory cortex (Luo 2019). The auditory cortex analyzes complex and biologically important sounds, from there signals are projected to other cortex areas.

Figure 41 Human brain, schematic drawing, coronal cut, showing auditory pathway (Luo, 2019)

Auditory signals are processed by multiple brainstem nuclei before reaching the thalamus and auditory cortex (Luo, 2019). The anatomical structures involved in the processing and perception of music are numerous (Luo, 2019, Reybrouck, 2021, Scherder 2017, Sugawa 2019), the structures identified as part of the auditory pathway that makes hearing possible indicated in the previous figure are the following:

→ Cochlear nuclei

The cochlear nuclei are located in the pons, part of the metencephalon, which in turn is part of the hindbrain. The cochlear nuclei receive the auditory signals from the auditory or cochlear nerve.

→ Superior olivary nuclei

The superior olivary nuclei are located in the pons, part of the metencephalon, which in turn is part of the hindbrain.

- Lateral lemniscus
The lateral lemniscus is located in the rhombencephalon or hindbrain.
- Inferior colliculus
The inferior colliculus is located in the mesencephalon or midbrain.
- Medial geniculate nuclei
The medial geniculate nuclei are located in the thalamus, which is part of the diencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain.
- Auditory cortex
The auditory cortex is located on the middle temporal gyrus of the temporal lobe, it processes the auditory information. The language center there is also used to appreciate music, generally, language is interpreted in the left hemisphere while music is interpreted in the right.

Then from the auditory cortex and possibly from the basal ganglia as well (Reybrouck, 2021) auditory signals are further relayed to other areas of the brain that play a role in the perception of music.

- Reticular formation
The reticular formation is located in the mesencephalon or midbrain, it is a network of neurons involved in alertness and attention.
- Amygdala,
The amygdala are part of the basal ganglia or cerebral nuclei and are thus located in the telencephalon which is part of the forebrain. The amygdala mediates emotion and motivation.
- Hypothalamus.
The hypothalamus is located under the thalamus, which is part of the diencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain. The hypothalamus is the center of homeostasis and connects the endocrine system to the nervous system. It plays a role in autonomic arousal following external stimuli.
- Broca's area
Broca's area is located in the frontal lobe of the cerebral hemisphere. The frontal lobe is used in thinking, decision-making and planning. Broca's area enables both speech and the expression of music. Broca's area occurs most commonly in the left cerebral hemisphere.
- Wernicke's area
Wernicke's area is located in the temporal lobe and enables the comprehension of spoken and written language as well as comprehension of music. Wernicke's area occurs most commonly in the left cerebral hemisphere.
- Nucleus accumbens
The nucleus accumbens is part of the basal ganglia or cerebral nuclei located in each hemisphere and is part of the reward system of the brain. The nucleus accumbens releases the neurotransmitter dopamine when listening to music.

- **Hippocampus**
The hippocampus part of the telencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain. The hippocampus produces and retrieves memories, is involved in learning and regulates emotional responses.
- **Putamen**
The putamen is a component of the basal ganglia, part of the telencephalon and forebrain. It processes rhythm and coordinates body movement.

A special case here is the occipital lobe. The occipital lobe has the primary visual cortex and processes visual stimuli from the eyes. Professional musicians use the occipital lobe also when listening to music, while non musicians use just the temporal lobe i.e., the auditory and language centres. This suggests that musicians might visualize the performing musicians or the music score when listening to music.

The individual structures of the auditory pathway can relatively easy be looked up in the online BrainSpan Atlas of the human brain, part of the Allen Brain Atlas. In this atlas one can easily navigate a hierarchy of anatomical structures and also search with the name of an anatomical structure.

Figure 42 Medial geniculate nucleus, in rectangle, screenshot from BrainSpan Atlas of a whole human brain.

The auditory pathway in depth

Auditory signals are processed by multiple brainstem nuclei before reaching the thalamus. (Luo 2019, p. 242-255) The cochlea is the start of the auditory pathway. Axons of spiral ganglion neurons terminate at the brainstem's dorsal and ventral cochlear nuclei. Neurons in the dorsal cochlear nucleus transfer information to the contralateral inferior colliculus of the midbrain, either directly or via intermediary neurons in the lateral lemniscus. Auditory impulses from the left and right ears are initially integrated in the superior olivary nuclei on both the ipsilateral and contralateral sides of the brainstem, where projection neurons in the ventral cochlear nucleus provide information. Additionally, projection neurons from the superior olivary nuclei end in the inferior colliculus, an essential area for integrating all auditory data. From there, auditory information is transmitted from the inferior colliculus to the auditory cortex in the temporal lobe via the medial geniculate nucleus of the thalamus. The auditory pathway ends in the auditory cortex.

In a recent study (Ciesla, 2020) the subsequent biopotentials or electrical signals in the anatomical structures of the auditory pathway together with their lag times have been put together in one infographic. It takes 50-300 ms for a signal to travel from cochlea to the auditory cortex.

Figure 43 Biopotentials generated in the auditory pathway: LLR (late-latency responses) 50–300 ms, MLR (medium-latency responses) 12–50 ms, ABR (Auditory Brainstem Responses) 1–12 ms; ECochG (electrocochleographic responses) 1.5 ms (Ciesla, 2020)

The biopotentials generated in the auditory pathway:

- LLR (late-latency responses) – responses from auditory cortex, latency of 50–300 ms;
- MLR (medium-latency responses, latency of 12–50 ms);
- ABR (Auditory Brainstem Responses, early potentials, latency of 1–12 ms);
- ECochG (electrocochleographic responses, latency circa 1.5 ms).

(Ciesla, 2020)

The auditory cortex relays signals to several other brain areas. (Koelsch 2011) In a more recent publication (Reybrouck, 2021) the basal ganglia are credited for relaying auditory information to other brain areas. The figure below illustrates the role of the basal ganglia.

Figure 44 Auditory projections in the brain here depicted schematically. The auditory pathway that transmits information about music from the ear to the brain is depicted in green, while projections to regions associated with emotion and arousal are shown in red (Reybrouck, 2021).

Physiology

A brief discussion of the underlying principles of the electrical activity of neurons, membrane potential, action potential, neurotransmitter release and neural communication is given by the following text box.

Neural communication - Hodgkin and Huxley

At the cellular level neurons use changes in membrane potential and neurotransmitter release to communicate. Ion channels and transport proteins move ions passively or actively across neuron cell membranes. The cell membranes of neurons are electrically polarized because of ion gradients across the membrane and differential permeability. Active transport of Na⁺ and K⁺ ions across the cell membrane of a neuron results in polarization of the membrane, maintaining a potential difference across the membrane called the resting potential. The binding of a neurotransmitter released by another neuron and diffusing across the synaptic cleft of a synapse results in the opening of ligand gated ion channels, influx of Ca²⁺ ions and further polarization of the cell membrane of the cell body of the neuron. When the cell membrane potential reaches a threshold value, voltage gated Na⁺ ion channels in the axon of the neuron open resulting in the influx of Na⁺ and a transient steep polarization peak followed by the opening of also voltage gated K⁺ ion channels, K⁺ efflux and a likewise steep depolarization called an action potential. The action potential travels along the axon towards the synapse at the end it where it elicits Ca²⁺ influx through voltage gated ion channels and subsequent release of neurotransmitter. After the action potential the cell membrane of the neuron repolarizes again towards the resting potential through the action of aforementioned active transport. This process has been described in a mathematical model by Hodgkin and Huxley in 1952 which earned them the Nobel prize in 1963. This process renders neurons and organisms having neurons the property of excitability i.e. being able to perceive and respond to a stimulus fast. The myelination of the axons of motor neurons allows for so-called saltatory conduction, greatly increasing the speed of propagation of the action potential and making motor responses even faster. (Luo, 2019, Mason, 2019) At the tissue level brain waves may have a role in communicating or coordinating activity of neural tissue from one area to another. See text box Brain waves.

Neurotransmitters

Neurotransmitters are an important aspect of the physiology of the nervous system in general including the processing of music in the brain. A neurotransmitter that has had a lot of attention in literature on music and the brain is dopamine (Reybrouck, 2021). When people listen to music, they feel a variety of emotions and an overall sense of well-being. Using brain imaging technology, researchers found that music-evoked pleasure is linked to dopamine release in the brain's reward regions (Beccacece, 2021, Reybrouck, 2021).

Figure 45 Chemical structure of Dopamine ([PubChem](#))

The nucleus accumbens, previously mentioned, part of the reward system of the brain, releases the neurotransmitter dopamine in response to music, mediating the pleasure one can experience when listening to music.

At the other end of the auditory pathway, the inner hair cells of the organ of Corti in the cochlea release the neurotransmitter glutamate, mediating auditory signals to neurons of the spiral ganglion and auditory nerve.

Figure 46 Chemical structure of Glutamate ([PubChem](#))

Perception

Perception is the conscious perceiving of sensed stimuli; many sensed stimuli are not consciously perceived. Perception is entirely about interpretation. Perception occurs in the cerebral cortex. This means that the sensation of a stimulus by sensory cells and the perception of that stimulus further on by the brain are related but different entities.

Example:

Pitch, how high or low a sound is perceived to be, depends on many things beyond only the component frequencies. Therefore, it is possible to perceive a pitch that does not match any frequency present in a natural sound. And it is not true that the perceived pitch of a natural sound is always the lowest frequency present, i.e. the fundamental frequency. This is typically the case but there are many contextual factors that can alter perceived pitch beyond stimulus frequency. The perceptual magnitude does not always equal the stimulus intensity either, rather the perceived magnitude of a stimulus equals the proportion of the intensity of the stimulus of the intensity of the whole of similar stimuli in the background. So, we perceive relative loudness rather than absolute loudness of music. This is referred to as Weber's law (Mason, 2019).

Models

We have studied different models of how the brain processes music, made from different perspectives, to get an as good as possible understanding of this. We have studied models of how the brain processes music from functional, cognitive, and probabilistic perspectives. All models are simplified abstractions or approximations of reality, made from a particular point of view so no model has it all. "*All models are wrong, but some are useful*" (George E.P. Box, 1976)

A functional model

The processing of music by the brain involves different structures that process different perceptual, cognitive, and emotional components with a varying selectivity. In the model shown in the following image (Warren, 2008), the human auditory brain has a hierarchical organization, anatomically and functionally: areas that are lower in the hierarchy pass information to higher stages and often vice versa, and increasingly complex and/or abstract features are represented at each hierarchical stage.

Figure 47 *Functional model of music perception (Warren, 2008)*

The abbreviations in the previous image refer to the following anatomical structures, many of them part of the (extended) auditory pathway discussed earlier in this chapter:

- Frontal Lobe
- Heschl's Gyrus
- Limbic Circuit
- Middle Temporal Gyrus
- Parietal Lobe
- Planum Temporale
- Superior Temporal Gyrus
- Temporal Pole

This model illustrates the generally hierarchical nature of music processing, with areas beyond the primary auditory cortex representing increasingly sophisticated and abstract features. There appears to be a relative rather than absolute functional dominance of the right hemisphere for processing a variety of musical components. This also applies to the processing of distinct musical components by different brain regions within a hemisphere. The limbic system, the circuit that regulates emotional responses, is phylogenetically considerably older than the brain network responsible for the perceptual and cognitive processing of music. The limbic system consists of the amygdala, the hippocampus, and the subcortical and cortical connections between them. (Koelsch, 2011)

A neurocognitive model

A neurocognitive model (Honing, 2018) of Dutch origin, focusses on musicality and musical phenotypes, the underlying cognitive mechanisms being melodic cognition and rhythmic cognition.

Figure 48 Neurocognitive model of musicality (Honing, 2018)

In this model each box represents a (hypothetical) processing component connected by pathways to other processing components. The input consists of both musical and tactile stimuli as this model is about both consuming and producing music.

A probabilistic model

The idea that perception can be viewed as a statistical Bayesian process is the basis for a relatively new approach to understanding how the brain functions. The Predictive Coding of Music (PCM) model (Vuust 2014, 2022) describes the coherent processes of perception, action, emotion, and learning that occur when people listen to music. Bayesian statistics is a part of statistics that takes prior knowledge in consideration in probability. The next figure gives a simplified view of this model.

Figure 49 Predictive Coding of Music model (PCM) (Vuust, 2014, 2022)

The PCM model posits that both nature and nurture or biology and culture, together with past musical experiences, give rise to a predictive brain model or frame of reference for music. This predictive brain model is continuously tested against new musical experiences and updated where predicted perception proves erroneous, so the model is not only a predicting model but also a learning model. This means that through a dynamic relationship between music's predictive patterns, such as the buildup and release of tension in rhythm, melody, harmony, form, and other musical aspects, and the brain's ability to predict what will occur next, music is experienced and learned. The real-time brain model is dependent on cultural background, personal listening history, musical skill, context such as social environment, brain state including attentional state and emotion, and innate biological characteristics. The brain is constantly attempting to close the gap between its model of how to interpret music and the music it really hears. This renders music an ever-changing experience and a method of long-term learning (Vuust, 2014, Vuust 2022).

Summarizing, when exposed to a musical stimulus, the brain tries to predict what may follow, evaluating the likelihood of what may follow given past experiences embodied in the model, and adjusting the model where it proved wrong. In this model the brain uses conditional probabilities of events, or Bayesian statistics partially based on past experiences, to maintain an actual brain model or frame of reference of in this case music. The next text box explains Bayes's Theorem and its application in this model

Applied to music theory, an example may be the use of cadences. A perfect cadence feels finished because you or your brain model anticipated it. However, an imperfect or half cadence feels unnatural or unfinished because it is not what our brain model anticipated. A

good example of this in classical music is the “Serenade for Strings in E Major” by Antonin Dvorak. At the 2:00 time mark there is an imperfect cadence which does not feel finished. However, at the 6:00 mark, you hear the same cadence with only a small alteration in the last notes which makes it feel finished and thus a perfect cadence. Listen to the [“Serenade for Strings in E Major”](#) on Spotify.

Bayesian statistics

Bayesian statistics is based on **Bayes's Theorem**, which in turn is grounded in conditional probability. A conditional probability is a probability based on **prior knowledge**. The formula of Bayes's Theorem is simply this:

$$P(A|B) = \frac{P(B|A) \cdot P(A)}{P(B)}$$

- P(A) is the probability of event A occurring before we see any data, called the prior probability or prior.
- p(A|B) is what we want to calculate, the probability of event A occurring given the occurrence of event B, called the posterior.
- p(B|A) is the probability of event B occurring given the occurrence of event A, called the likelihood.
- p(B) is the probability of event B occurring in general, called the normalizing constant.

The application of Bayes's theorem in statistics is an area of statistics in itself i.e. Bayesian statistics. However, there is another way to think of Bayes's theorem. It gives us a way to update the probability of a hypothesis or model, in the light of some piece of data or in the case of music exposure to a musical stimulus. This way of thinking about Bayes's theorem is called the **diachronic interpretation**. Diachronic means that something is happening over time, here the probability of the hypothesis or model changes, over time, as we see new data or in the case of music are exposed to new musical stimuli (Downey, 2012). Ultimately Bayes's theorem gives us a way to maximize the probability of a hypothesis or model by continuously **updating** the hypothesis or **model** itself.

Predictive processing is a general theory of neural processing inspired by research in artificial intelligence and computational neuroscience. In brief, predictive processing proposes that perception and learning are Bayesian processes by which the brain attempts to minimize prediction errors. The figure shows a schematic illustration of what is called the computational architecture that underlies predictive coding in the brain. The left of the figure shows the basic motif of connections, via which prediction errors are formed by comparing bottom-up input with top-down predictions. These predictions can be of either the input or the predictability of that input. These are designated first-order and second-order predictions, respectively. The right part of the figure describes the resulting hierarchical message passing implicit in predictive coding, in which forward or ascending connections convey prediction errors to higher levels, while backward or descending connections supply the predictions that enable the computation of prediction errors in the lower level. There are two kinds of descending predictions in predictive coding, first-order prediction of content (grey arrows) and second-order predictions of context (blue arrows) or predictability of content.

Figure 50 Schematic illustration of what is called the computational architecture that underlies predictive coding in the brain (Vuust, 2022).

Neural networks

The PCM model resembles the feed-forward back-propagation design of artificial neural networks in artificial intelligence. In artificial intelligence the feed forward of calculated values and subsequent propagate back of the differences between calculated values and expected values to earlier layers in layered neural networks for adjustments there, establish a mechanism for learning (Luo, 2019). However, this resemblance may only be a superficial one, more in depth the brain possibly learns in a way different from artificial neural networks. There are doubts whether back-propagation can exist in biological neural networks in the brain (Fodor, 2022).

Figure 51 The differences between the brain models of two individuals may result in a different perception of the same musical stimulus (Vuust, 2022).

Imaging

There are several ways to assess, image and measure brain activity in a test subject. Two of these techniques are EEG and fMRI.

fMRI

Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) is a medical imaging technology that uses radio waves and magnetic fields. The subject lies in a strong magnetic field from a number of large current coils. The magnetic field affects the nuclei of the hydrogen atoms in the body. The hydrogen nucleus behaves like a magnet that is directed by the magnetic field of the coils. Due to the absorption of a pulse of radio waves of a certain frequency, the magnetic directions of the hydrogen nuclei vibrate around an equilibrium position and resonance occurs. After the pulse of radio waves, the directions of the hydrogen nuclei return to their equilibrium position in the magnetic field and thereby emit one photon of radio radiation per hydrogen nucleus. The antennas in the MRI scanner pick up these radio waves from the body. The phenomenon of magnetic resonance only occurs if the frequency of the radio waves matches the strength of the magnetic field. The 3D variation of the magnetic field and the associated variation of the frequency of the radio waves makes it possible to determine the location in the body where the signal received back has been transmitted. An MRI scan thus creates a 3D image of hydrogen concentrations in the body and can display any desired cross-section of the body on a screen (Flokstra, 2020). The spatial resolution of MRI is relatively large, the temporal resolution, on the other hand, is relatively small.

fMRI or functional MRI is an application of MRI in which the subject is exposed to a specific stimulus or has to perform a specific task, whereby the location of the associated or necessary brain activity is visualized on a screen with MRI. fMRI measures brain activity by detecting changes associated with blood flow. This technique relies on the fact that cerebral blood flow and brain activity are coupled. When an area of the brain is in use, blood flow to that region also increases. (Wikipedia)

Neurosynth is an online fMRI brain image database that features automated meta-analysis of selected fMRI studies for a number of keywords. We used an automated meta-analysis of 163 selected fMRI studies on neurosynth.org for the keyword music. A meta-analysis is the analysis of analysis already done in other studies. We further explored the results by shifting the x, y and z planes of the three sections, following along the auditory pathway from brainstem to cortex. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a lab report of this practical work.

Figure 52 Meta-analysis of 163 fMRI studies on neurosynth.org (Reybrouck, 2021)

The figure above is a meta-analysis (Reybrouck, 2021) performed on neurosynth.org of 163 studies employing fMRI technology and containing the keyword "music." The figure shows brain activity highlighted in orange, blue and green, for the perception, production and imagining of music respectively. Highlighted are regions associated with hearing (supratemporal cortex), motor control (dorsomedial prefrontal cortex and cerebellum), bodily awareness (insula), and reward (ventral striatum). Abbreviations: CRBL cerebellum, INS insula, MedFG medial frontal gyrus, PreCG precentral gyrus of primary motor cortex, PUT putamen, SPL superior parietal lobule, STG superior temporal gyrus of primary auditory cortex, THA thalamus, L left, R right, Z peak Z-value is a computational measure used in the

rendering of these images. The image demonstrates that the perception, production and imagining of music have both common and unique areas or structures of brain activity.

Figure 53 fMRI image of tonotopic organization of the auditory cortex (Ciesla, 2020)

The figure above shows the tonotopic organization of the auditory cortex. The organ of Corti in the cochlea ([Chapter 4](#)) and the auditory cortex both feature a tonotopic organization, meaning that the sensing and processing of a specific frequency is focused on a specific region along the length of the organ of Corti and on a specific region of the surface of the auditory cortex respectively. Colours indicate the regions with the highest activation in response to a given frequency of stimulation (Ciesla, 2020)

EEG

An individual neuron is on average an electrical dipole, with the cell body being positively charged and the axon negatively. The collective electrical activity of the brain results in observable potential differences across the scalp of a test subject. These potential differences are in an order of magnitude of around 100 uV. These potential differences can be measured with a set of electrodes and visualized using appropriate software, each electrode producing a trace of its potential difference varying over time. A recording of potential difference varying over time is called an electroencephalogram or EEG. EEG is beyond the reach of DIY neuroscience enthusiasts. Or so we thought. In recent years basic and affordable EEG devices as well as supporting software have become available, making the use of the long-proven EEG technology a feasible option for this study. This is the topic of [Chapter 6](#).

Conclusion

How is music processed in the brain? A general outline of an answer comes within reach. The brain processes music in possibly a predictive manner involving many interconnected pathways and networks, arranged in partly parallel hierarchies, including nuclei in the brain stem and the thalamus, the auditory cortex and other higher cortex areas, and also including the language processing areas Broca's area and Wernicke's area. The different perceptual components or constituents of music, pitch, melody, and harmony are processed partly through different pathways, eventually to be integrated in the auditory cortex. Areas beyond the auditory cortex connect perception with meaning and learning, as well as behavioral or motor reactions to music. The limbic system, somewhat parallel to the perceptual and cognitive processing hierarchies, elicits emotional responses to music.

Discussion

There are various approaches and various models employed in the scientific research of how the brain processes music. To get a good understanding of a field of inquiry it is helpful to do this from different viewpoints and using different approaches and methods. In this chapter we have attempted to compare and contrast some of these approaches and models and develop our own answer to the question of how the brain processes music. We have also found interesting parallels with language and language processing by the brain, briefly discussed in the text box on language research and Chomskyan linguistics in [Chapter 1](#) and in the next text box.

Language processing

The Hickok-Poeppel model (Hickok, Poeppel, 2007) is a neurobiological model of language processing that posits that there are two separate but interconnected systems for processing language. The first system, the phonological system, is responsible for processing the sound and structure of language. The second system, the semantic system, is responsible for processing the meaning of language.

Figure 54 The Hickok Poeppel model of language processing (Hickok, Poeppel, 2007)

Chapter 6

How do EEG recordings during exposure to a musical stimulus differ?

Introduction

How do EEG recordings during exposure to a musical stimulus, exposure to ambient noise and while in silent meditation differ and what does this signify? Recent studies have shown that listening to music or musical stimuli results in observable changes in brain activity while listening. These changes in brain activity were made visible with fMRI or EEG (Reybrouck, 2021, Schaefer, 2011, Segawa, 2018). This chapter will further explore the electrical activity of the brain and the electroencephalogram or EEG and how these respond to exposure to a musical stimulus.

The principles underlying the electrical activity of an individual neuron have been described in the previous chapter. The electrical activity of the brain as a whole is the result of the collective electrical activity of numerous individual neurons, primarily collective post-synaptic potential changes. The electrical activity of the brain as a whole is the collective result of electrical activity of individual neurons and produces detectable electrical potential changes over the scalp of a test subject. These potential differences have a magnitude of around 100 μ V. These potential differences can be monitored with a series of electrodes and viewed with the proper software, with each electrode generating a trace of its electrical potential difference's time-dependent variation or oscillation. An electroencephalogram, or EEG, is a recording of potential difference fluctuations across time. Certain patterns can be recognized in an electroencephalogram, EEG; these patterns are known as brain waves. The next paragraphs will further elaborate on EEG and its application as well as the EEG device and EEG software used in this study.

Oscillations in local electrical field potential are possibly a mechanism of communication and coordination within the brain. Within an area, cellular firing or spiking neurons are locked to the oscillations of the local electrical field potential. Since oscillations possibly govern the timing of neural firing, they possibly communicate information and create distributed representations of information. Two nearby brain regions that oscillate in sync will have neurons that also fire in sync, which may also mean the excitation or inhibition of the neurons they connect to will be stronger (Mathewson, 2022).

Figure 55 Neurons firing in synchrony, collectively generating oscillating local electrical potentials. (Mathewson, 2022)

The oscillations in local electrical potentials of the brain also known as brainwaves have a number of fundamental frequency bands that are differentially influenced by cognitive processes and vice versa. In literature there are five frequency bands distinguished: delta (1-3 Hz), theta (4-7 Hz), alpha (8-12 Hz), beta (12-30 Hz), and gamma (30-100 Hz). In auditory attention experiments alpha band activity has been shown to be related to aspects of music processing, in particular increase of (occipital) alpha band activity has been shown to be a possible indicator of auditory attention (Loui & Guetta, 2019, Schaefer, 2011, Segawa 2018).

Brain waves

Recent research has linked attention to brain waves. In the early 20th century, the German psychiatrist Hans Berger invented the electroencephalogram or EEG and popularized the theory that electrical activity of the human and mammalian brain has innate rhythmic oscillations. These oscillations might enable long-range neural communication and coordination in the brain.

The different frequency bands of brainwaves are associated with different brain states. When we focus attention on something externally, the relative power in the alpha frequency band goes down and that of the beta frequency band goes up. The relative power in the gamma frequency band is associated with neural activity in general. The relative power in the theta frequency band increases during spatial navigation and is associated with learning and memory. The relative power in the alpha frequency band is associated with (internally directed) attention, rest and relaxation and inhibition of (other) neural activity. (Mathewson, 2022)

We found some contradictions in published literature as to how alpha frequency band power relates to attention, with some publications stating an increase of alpha power during attention and other the opposite. This may be explained by that there is a possible distinction between externally focused attention and internally focused attention. It is thought that internal focus increases alpha band power or vice versa and external focus decreases alpha band power. The question is then whether the perception of music requires internal or external attention. Or both? Listening to music may well be both, as listening itself requires an external focus while trying to interpret the music and additionally imagining the performing musicians or the music score may require an internal focus. Schaefer (2011) reports a significant alpha band power increase in test subjects imagining music in silence and a less strong alpha band power increase in test subjects listening to the actual music. This could be interpreted as that imagining music silently requires only internal attention while listening requires both internal and external attention.

Brain waves play a particular role in the perception of rhythm. The relative power in the beta frequency band has been shown to follow the beat in rhythmic music perception and imagery. Rhythmic synchronization to the beat frequency of music is highest over the motor regions, which is consistent with fMRI research. Bursts of beta band activity begin in the left sensory motor cortex and influence auditory cortex activity, suggesting the motor system controls rhythmic attention in the auditory system. Recent research reveals that musical rhythm drives auditory attention by entraining oscillatory neural activity that begins in the motor system but is intimately connected with the auditory system. These findings may also apply to speech, which comprises various rhythmic or temporal modulations at specific frequencies (Loui & Guetta, 2019).

We have purchased and successfully used a modest EEG device (**Muse2™**) and open-source EEG analysis software (**EEGLAB**) for this study, this is further reported on in this chapter. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) gives a complete and detailed lab report of this practical work.

Research question

How different is brain activity during exposure to a musical stimulus? This was the initial research question for this chapter. With EEG recording and analysis at our disposal, we have made the research question of this chapter more specific as follows:

How do EEG recordings during exposure to a musical stimulus, exposure to ambient noise and while in silent meditation differ in the power of the alpha frequency band and what does this signify?

Hypothesis

Our hypothesis is that the exposure to a musical stimulus will require both internal and external attention, which in turn will lead to some increase of the power in the EEG alpha frequency band as compared to exposure to ambient noise or silent meditation.

Language, music, and attention

In a recent study (Segawa, 2019), groups of students were presented a song in Spanish familiar to them in English. There were three groups: native English speakers, native English speakers studying Spanish and native Spanish speakers. The outcomes were as follows: Native English speakers showed little alpha band activity, possibly because they did not try to interpret what was sung in the music clip. Native Spanish speakers similarly showed minimal alpha band activity because listening to music in a language they are proficient in does not require internal attention because it is easily comprehended. Interestingly, native English speakers learning Spanish showed significant alpha band activity, possibly because they grasp the language to a certain extent but require internal attention in order to comprehend what is being sung.

Figure 56 Effects of language experience on attention (Segawa, 2019)

All speakers exhibited a substantial difference both in their left and right hemispheres, but only for the first time the music was performed, possibly because the second time the song was played it had become familiar already and did not demand attention.

Expected results

If our hypothesis is true, we expect to find the highest power in the alpha frequency band of the EEG of the test subject exposed to a musical stimulus.

Methods

EEG

Electroencephalography, or EEG, is a technique used to measure the electrical activity of the brain. In EEG, electrodes are most commonly placed on the scalp of a subject. Typically, EEG does not record the activity of single neurons, but rather detects the signals created when populations of neurons are active at the same time, as described in the introduction of this chapter. It mostly records signals from small areas of the brain surrounding each electrode. EEG primarily measures collective postsynaptic potential changes, which are changes in membrane potential of neurons caused by neurotransmitters binding to receptors on the postsynaptic membrane, and not action potentials. (Mathewson, 2022)

EEG provides a visual representation of the brain's electrical activity as waves of changing frequency, amplitude, and shape. It can be used to measure brain activity that occurs during an event, such as the presentation of a stimulus, as well as spontaneous brain activity that occurs when no event is occurring or while performing a task. (Mathewson, 2022)

To measure the spatial distribution of the potential differences, electrodes are placed in a regular grid covering the surface of the head. Each location is given a name, with the letter indicating the location on the head: frontal, central, parietal, temporal, occipital and fronto-polar. The suffix has a letter z if along the midline, an odd number over the left hemisphere and an even number over the right. The numbers start along the midline and get higher for more lateral sites on the head. The black electrode is the reference the other electrodes are measured against. There are several nomenclatures or standards for the numbering and placement of the electrodes. Due to its great temporal precision, the analysis of cortical electrical impulses is a useful technique for studying brain function. (Gonzales, 2020)

EEG has several advantages, including its low cost and capacity to record brain activity on the order of milliseconds with excellent temporal resolution, but it also has certain disadvantages. Due to the fact that EEG monitors activity in broad groups of neurons, it is difficult to pinpoint EEG-observed brain activity to a specific place, resulting in poor spatial resolution. It also only records the activity of neurons in the cortex, its ability to record activity in deeper brain areas is limited. (Dingman, 2019)

The raw EEG signal is, like music, a periodic but nonharmonic function and a composite of many underlying harmonic functions or fundamental frequencies and, like music, can be decomposed into a spectrogram using Fourier transformation. Our Lab notebook (Attachment) has a textbox dedicated to Fourier analysis. The result of performing a Fourier analysis on EEG data can be visualized in a frequency-power diagram, as shown in the results paragraph of this chapter.

The next image shows the whole EEG trace and below it the constituent frequency bands, with frequency on the horizontal axis and relative power on the vertical axis.

Figure 57 EEG frequency bands (Mathewson, 2022)

EEG device

The EEG device measures the difference in electrical potential across each of its electrodes and the reference electrode. The EEG device amplifies the analog signal and converts it to a digital signal. The digital signal now has discrete time steps and discrete differences in voltage. The sampling rate controls how many samples of voltage per second (Hz) are recorded. The Muse2™ records 256 samples per second when set to a constant recording. In the case of wireless EEG, like the Muse2™, the EEG device transmits the signal to the recording device. The Muse2™ headset features four electrodes: AF7, AF8, TP9 and TP10, shown in the following image.

Figure 58 Muse2™ headset (a) and placement of electrodes (b) AF7, AF8, TP9 and TP10 (Mansi, 2021)

Experimental design

We performed six single-subject experiments over a period of time, eventually consolidated into one study, with the following conditions: silent meditation, exposure to ambient noise and exposure to a trumpet solo in a fragment of jazz music, all conditions with earphones in and eyes closed. EEG recording were made with a Muse2™ EEG headband by InterAxon® and the Mind Monitor® app and subsequent analysis was done with EEGLAB software. Additionally, computation of the average power in alpha frequency band for all experiments combined was done with the MATLAB script read_muse.m (Segawa, 2019) reused with permission by the author. All experiments are documented in our [Lab Logbook](#) (Attachment).

Participants

We performed a series of six similar experiments on a single participant.

Figure 59 Test subject wearing Muse2™ headset (Photograph by authors)

Figure 60 Muse2™ headset used in this study (Photograph by authors)

Stimuli

After silent meditation (40s), the test subject was exposed to a fragment (40s) of ambient cafeteria noise ([YouTube](#)) followed by a musical fragment (40s) from the trumpet solo of “Sandu” performed by Clifford Brown on his album *Study in Brown* (1955).

Equipment

- Muse2™ headset by InterAxon
- Earphones

- Mind Monitor app
- EEGLAB software
- MATLAB script read_muse.m
- MATLAB r2022a, Student license

Procedure

In all experiments the test subject was seated with earphones in and eyes closed in a quiet room. The EEG recordings for the three different conditions silent meditation, ambient noise and musical stimulus in a single experiment, were done one after the other separated by a brief pause.

Analysis

The analysis of the recorded data was done with EEGLAB software in MATLAB[®]. Additionally, computation of the average power in alpha frequency band for all experiments combined was done with MATLAB[®] script read_muse.m (Segawa, 2019).

Results

Sample data

The following table shows selected columns of the first 10 rows of a Mind Monitor data file of this experiment (Exp. 06). EEGLab uses the RAW data columns, the other columns are used by the Mind Monitor app itself.

TimeStamp	Alpha_TP9	Alpha_AF7	Alpha_AF8	Alpha_TP10	RAW_TP9	RAW_AF7	RAW_AF8	RAW_TP10	HSL_TP9	HSL_AF7	HSL_AF8	HSL_TP10
2022-03-27 17:18:46.651	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	823.9927	804.65204	811.50183	821.5751	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.652	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	822.381	802.6374	806.26373	819.15753	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.653	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	821.1722	799.41394	796.5934	813.5165	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.653	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	820.7692	801.4286	799.81683	806.26373	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.653	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	818.3516	805.05493	807.47253	807.0696	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.653	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	819.5604	805.4579	805.4579	813.5165	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.654	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	824.7985	806.26373	800.2198	825.2015	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.654	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	827.2161	810.293	804.65204	819.5604	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.654	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	828.8278	812.71063	801.8315	809.4872	1	1	1	1
2022-03-27 17:18:46.655	0.7591723	0.15509331	0.9167431	0.693591	826.4103	812.3077	795.78754	814.7253	1	1	1	1

Our Lab Notebook (Attachment) gives a full specification of the data files produced by the Mind Monitor app.

Sample EEG trace

The following image shows a test EEG recording (Exp. 02) of our initial use of the Muse2[™] headset during eye-closed meditation. Each electrode is represented by a separate trace in the image. The traces show little, or no artifacts caused by muscle activity and are thus a good sample EEG. On the horizontal axis time (ms), on the vertical axis electrical potential difference (mV). The graph was made with EEGLAB software.

Figure 61 Sample EEG made with Muse2™ headset, recorded with the Mind Monitor® app and visualized with EEGLAB software. (Exp. 02)

Individual level

Results at the level of an individual experiment. Here we chose the condition background noise as control for the condition musical stimulus. The following graph shows a spectrogram with so-called scalp plots at selected frequencies for a single experiment of a test subject exposed to ambient noise with frequency (Hz) on the horizontal axis and the absolute power ($10 * \log_{10}(\mu V^2/Hz)$) on the vertical axis. The graph was made with EEGLAB software.

Figure 62 Spectrogram with scalp plots for the condition exposure to ambient noise (Exp. 06).

In all but one plot, including the plot for the alpha band (10.0 Hz), the most activity is in the occipital region of the brain. The primary visual cortex of the brain is located in the occipital lobe. The spectrograms for each of the four electrodes show that the recordings after processing still contain some noise.

The graph below shows the spectrogram with so-called scalp plots at selected frequencies for a single experiment with a test subject exposed to a musical stimulus with the frequency (Hz) on the horizontal axis and the absolute power ($10 * \log_{10}(\mu V^2/Hz)$) on the vertical axis. The graph was made with EEGLAB software.

Figure 63 Spectrogram with scalp plots for the condition exposure to musical stimulus (Exp. 06).

In all scalp plots, including the plot for the alpha band (10.0 Hz), the most activity is in the right frontotemporal region of the brain. The frontotemporal region of the brain is responsible for the processing of higher, abstract function of the brain. This is also the approximate location of Broca's area and Wernicke's area, which are found in the left cerebral hemisphere in 90% of right-handed individuals and 70% of left-handed individuals (Oxford Dictionary of Biology, 2015). The test subject in this experiment is left-handed. The spectrograms for each of the four electrodes show that the recordings after processing still contain some noise. Note that the vertical scale of both images is different.

Group level

EEGLAB

Results at the level of a group of individual experiments pooled in one analysis (Exp. 12). Here we chose the condition background noise as control for the condition musical stimulus. The graph below shows the spectrogram for in EEGLAB the pooled data of six identical experiments 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 into one study, with the test subject being exposed to ambient noise or a musical stimulus respectively, with the frequency (Hz) on the horizontal axis and the power ($10 * \log_{10}(\mu V^2)$) on the vertical axis. The graphs were made with EEGLAB software.

Figure 64 Spectrograms for the pooled data in EEGLAB of six identical experiments 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 into one study, with statistical significance indication underneath.

The black bars underneath the graphs indicate the frequency ranges where the difference between the response to background noise and music stimulus is statistically significant. The differences appear small. However, the vertical scale is a logarithmic scale. Statistical significance is further explained in a textbox in our Lab Notebook (Attachment). It is not possible to draw conclusions from these graphs. This is why a second approach for analysis of EEG data was used.

MATLAB script `read_muse.m`

Results at the level of a group of individual experiments pooled in one analysis (Exp. 12), now analyzed with a MATLAB script (Segawa, 2019). Here, as opposed to the analysis with EEGLAB, we chose the condition silent meditation as control for the conditions ambient noise and musical stimulus. The mean values for the power in the alpha frequency band, for each electrode TP9, AF7, AF8 and TP10, and for selected intervals of individual experiments, were calculated with the MATLAB script `read_muse.m` (Segawa, 2019). The summary statistics and test statistics were calculated in the Jupyter notebook `PWS_Exp12_Plot` (Attachment). Only relatively noise free 10-second intervals of the recordings, identified in the EEG plots also generated by this script, were analyzed, time intervals are included in the tables for reproducibility.

Power ($10^{*10} \log \mu V^2/Hz$) in alpha frequency band (8-10 Hz) for TP9 electrode						
	Subject in silent meditation		Subject exposed to cafeteria background noise		Subject exposed to jazz trumpet solo	
	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean
Exp. 02	70s-80s	0.7749	NA	NA	NA	NA
Exp. 06	NA	NA	37s-47s	0.4951	0s-10s	1.2429
Exp. 07	15s-25s	1.0258	30s-40s	1.3445	10s-20s	1.3572
Exp. 09	13s-23s	0.8813	27s-37s	1.5182	0s-10s	1.4504
Exp. 10	17s-27s	1.4883	18s-28s	2.3242	25s-35s	1.8600
Exp. 11	30s-40s	2.2414	0s-10s	2.0975	20s-30s	2.0956
median		1.0258		1.5182		1.4504
mean		1.2823		1.5559		1.6012
sd		0.5378		0.6411		0.3231
n		5		5		5
t-statistic		--		-1.2681		-2.5876
p-value		--		0.2736		0.0608

Table 1: Summary of measurements of experiments 2, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 for TP9 electrode.

Power ($10^{*10}\log \mu V^2/Hz$) in alpha frequency band (8-10 Hz) for AF7 electrode						
	Subject in silent meditation		Subject exposed to cafeteria background noise		Subject exposed to jazz trumpet solo	
	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean
Exp. 02	70s-80s	-5.2224	NA	NA	NA	NA
Exp. 06	NA	NA	37s-47s	-7.2144	0s-10s	-4.7508
Exp. 07	15s-25s	-6.3895	30s-40s	-5.6551	10s-20s	-7.9886
Exp. 09	13s-23s	-6.6267	27s-37s	-5.8297	0s-10s	-6.5942
Exp. 10	17s-27s	-6.7734	18s-28s	-5.1032	25s-35s	-5.4738
Exp. 11	30s-40s	-6.0884	0s-10s	-7.2452	20s-30s	-6.5998
median		-6.3895		-5.8297		-6.5942
mean		-6.2201		-6.2095		-6.2814
sd		0.5501		0.8669		1.1053
n		5		5		5
t-statistic		--		-0.0155		0.1264
p-value				0.9884		0.9055

Table 2: Summary of measurements of experiments 2, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 for AF7 electrode.

Power ($10^{*10}\log \mu V^2/Hz$) in alpha frequency band (8-10 Hz) for AF8 electrode						
	Subject in silent meditation		Subject exposed to cafeteria background noise		Subject exposed to jazz trumpet solo	
	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean
Exp. 02	70s-80s	-5.0653	NA	NA	NA	NA
Exp. 06	NA	NA	37s-47s	-1.8196	0s-10s	NA ²
Exp. 07	15s-25s	-4.5743	30s-40s	-4.7106	10s-20s	-5.2632
Exp. 09	13s-23s	-4.1852	27s-37s	-3.7875	0s-10s	-5.5422
Exp. 10	17s-27s	-5.3505	18s-28s	-5.2220	25s-35s	-5.9074
Exp. 11	30s-40s	-6.4969	0s-10s	-5.6064	20s-30s	-4.5890
median		-5.0653		-4.7106		-5.4027
mean		-5.1344		-4.2292		-5.3254
sd		0.7903		1.3502		0.4827
n		5		5		4
t-statistic		--		-1.4858		0.2428
p-value		--		0.2115		0.8238

Table 3: Summary of measurements of experiments 2, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 for AF8 electrode.

² Signal of AF8 electrode disturbed by probably muscle activity.

Figure 65 EEG at the 0s-10s interval for experiment 6 with test subject exposed to musical stimulus, showing disturbed signal at the AF8 electrode, probably due to muscle activity of eyes or mouth, visualized with MATLAB script read_muse.m (Segawa, 2019).

Power ($10^{10} \log \mu V^2/Hz$) in alpha frequency band (8-10 Hz) for TP10 electrode						
	Subject in silent meditation		Subject exposed to cafeteria background noise		Subject exposed to jazz trumpet solo	
	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean	Interval	Mean
Exp. 02	70s-80s	0.6719	NA	NA	NA	NA
Exp. 06	NA	NA	37s-47s	0.7834	0s-10s	0.1494
Exp. 07	15s-25s	1.4549	30s-40s	2.0835	10s-20s	1.2403
Exp. 09	13s-23s	3.8143	27s-37s	1.8498	0s-10s	1.8738
Exp. 10	17s-27s	2.3109	18s-28s	3.7283	25s-35s	2.5318
Exp. 11	30s-40s	3.2459	0s-10s	2.5331	20s-30s	3.8185
median		2.3109		2.0835		1.8738
mean		2.2996		2.1956		1.9228
sd		1.1448		0.9581		1.2311
n		5		5		5
t-statistic		--		0.1792		0.8701
p-value		--		0.8665		0.4334

Table 4: Summary of measurements of experiments 2, 6, 7, 9, 10 and 11 for TP10 electrode.

In the Jupyter notebook **PWS_Exp12_Plot** we used a **paired t-test** to evaluate whether the differences between the group means are statistically significant. A t-test is used when you have a dependent quantitative variable and an independent categorical variable. The paired t-test compares two means of measurements taken from the same subject. The Student's t-test is further explained in a separate text box.

Figure 66: The above graphs were made with the Python library Matplotlib in the Jupyter notebook PWS_Exp12_Plot. Note that the vertical axes have a logarithmic scale.

Student's t-test

The Student's t-test is a statistical test that tests whether a difference between two means is (statistically) significant, under the assumptions that values approximately have a Normal distribution. The test not only takes into consideration the value of the difference between the means but also the number of observation or samples and the variability occurring within the observations or samples. The t-test calculates the ratio between the difference between two group means and the variability within the groups called the t-value.

$$t = \frac{|x_1 - x_2|}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{(s_1)^2}{n_1} + \frac{(s_2)^2}{n_2}\right)}}$$

The t is the t-value, x_1 and x_2 are the means of the observations or samples in each group, s_1 and s_2 are the standard deviations of the observations or samples in each group and n_1 and n_2 are the number of observations or samples in each group. The null hypothesis H_0 that there is no statistical significance is accepted as long as the t-value does not exceed the critical value, when the t-value does exceed the critical value the alternative hypothesis H_1 that there indeed is a significant difference is accepted. Summarizing, to be statistically significant, an observed difference must have a t-value higher than a critical value. Statistical significance is further explained in a separate text box in our [Lab notebook](#) (Attachment). We have used the paired t-test since we have observations or samples for different conditions for the same test subject.

Conclusion

At the level of an individual experiment, we observed a decrease of occipital alpha power and an increase in frontotemporal alpha power on the right side for exposure to a musical stimulus compared to exposure to ambient noise. It is striking that this is the case not only for the alpha frequency band but for all frequency bands. This analysis of spectrogram and scalp plots needs to be reproduced sufficient times before any conclusions can be drawn

At the level of grouped results of individual experiments, we observed spectral power differences between both the conditions exposure to cafeteria noise and exposure to a trumpet solo compared to the control condition silent meditation. The spectral power differences found in the alpha frequency band suggest that both the conditions exposure to cafeteria noise and exposure to a trumpet solo require internal directed attention, manifested in an increase in the power in the alpha frequency band as compared to the control condition silent meditation. These findings support our hypothesis. The increase surprisingly is strongest for cafeteria noise, suggesting that it triggers imagination more than a (familiar) piece of music.

The observed differences between the group means for the conditions silent meditation and cafeteria noise and between the group means for the conditions silent meditation and trumpet solo are encouraging but at this time not statistically significant, with the difference between the conditions silent meditation and trumpet solo found for electrode TP9 closest ($p=0.06$) to statistical significance

Discussion

At the level of an individual experiment, in scalp plots we observed a decrease in occipital power and an increase in frontotemporal power for all frequency bands. The cause for this has not been clarified yet. More experiments will be needed to investigate the reproducibility of these findings.

At the level of grouped results of individual experiments, the increase in the power of the alpha frequency band surprisingly is strongest for cafeteria noise, suggesting that it triggers imagination more than a (familiar) piece of music. To the test subject involved the fragment of jazz music was well-known. This may have impacted the magnitude of the alpha response somewhat negatively. This is explained in textbox Language, Music, and Attention of this chapter. In future experiments, the musical stimuli should be new to the test subjects. Only a new musical stimulus will elicit internal attention and thus increase in alpha response.

There is a to be a notable difference at the level of grouped results for the power in the alpha frequency band between the units of the results obtained from EEGLAB and the units of the results obtained from the MATLAB script (Segawa, 2019). However, the first renders power spectrum ($10^{10} \log \mu V^2$), the latter spectral power density ($10^{10} \log \mu V^2/Hz$). It is clear that it is very important to understand how computations are done by the software used in order to be able to draw valid conclusions from its output.

Our adjusted hypothesis is that exposure to a musical stimulus will require more internally directed than externally directed attention, which will lead to increase of the power in the EEG alpha frequency band, provided the musical stimulus is both of interest and new to the test subject and is not repeatedly used.

Overall, the design of a good experiment proved very difficult. In retrospect, silent meditation might not have been the best choice for a control condition, since a base level of alpha frequency band activity already comes with this condition. In retrospect, we also conclude that there are many hidden variables, for example knowledge of or experience with the musical stimulus, but also general musical experience, meaning if a test subject is a musician or a non-musician. These variables impact the elicitation of internal and/or external attention and thereby the result of the experiment.

The practical execution of the experiments and the analysis of the results proved to be somewhat less difficult than initially thought. The usage of the Muse2™ headset together with the Mind Monitor® app turned out relatively user friendly. The analysis of data with EEGLAB has a steep learning curve, however there is a lot of online material and an active user community who can and will help. The challenge her was obtaining recordings without too much noise and the subsequent removal of noise. The indispensable additional analysis of data with the MATLAB® script read-muse.m (Segawa, 2019) was also relatively easy, the script itself being well documented.

From the initial research question of this chapter, we derived several specific questions, from which we chose to answer one. However, the remaining questions are left unanswered and are worthwhile to explore later. Questions for further research:

- a) What are the observable effects, if any, on the EEG of a test subject exposed to a specific musical stimulus e.g. does exposure to a certain rhythm result in alpha entrainment, which is a kind of resonance? (Mathewson, 2022)

- b) What are the observable effects, if any, on the ERP of test subjects exposed to a brief discrete musical stimulus e.g. consonance or dissonance, made visible with ERP? (Bouwer, 2021)

ERP

ERP uses the electrical activity evoked by individual presentations of stimuli that creates small changes in electrical voltage. These changes are, however, very small, about 1-10 microVolts (μV), and the noise from other activity like eye movements and other muscle activity is sometimes 10 times as large. This noise can be mitigated by averaging this evoked activity over many repeated presentations of the same stimulus. This average voltage in response to a stimulus is called an Event-related potential (ERP) or evoked potential (EP) (Mathewson, 2022).

- c) How does the emotional state of a test subject exposed to a musical stimulus, as reflected by the observed heart rate, differ from the emotional state of a test subject exposed to ambient noise or is in silent meditation? Ideally in an experiment EEG and ECG/heart rate are recorded simultaneously.

ECG

The phenomenon of bioelectricity is not only found in neural cells and neural tissue but also in muscle cells and tissue. There are claims (Mathewson, 2022) that the Muse2™ EEG device can be used to generate a simple electrocardiogram or ECG as well, simulating the Einthoven triangle, fundamental for ECG, by holding its center and AF7 electrodes between the fingertips of the right and left hand respectively. This makes it possible to record heart rate and ECG of a test subject as well, and since heart rate reflects emotional state, record changes if any in the emotional state of a test subject when exposed to a musical stimulus.

General conclusion

How does the brain process music? How the brain processes music can be studied from various perspectives: (evolutionary) genetics, (comparative) anatomy, physiology, computational science, and psychology, each with its own methods and models. The ability to process music and to make music requires many traits, many of these traits have been passed on to us by our predecessors in evolution. The brain processes music in possibly a predictive manner, involving many interconnected pathways and networks, arranged in partly parallel hierarchies, including nuclei in the brain stem and the thalamus, the auditory cortex and other cortex areas, and also including the language processing areas Broca's area and Wernicke's area. The different perceptual components or constituents of music, pitch, melody, and harmony are processed partly through different pathways, eventually to be integrated in the auditory cortex. Areas beyond the auditory cortex connect perception with meaning and learning, as well as behavioral or motor reactions to music. The limbic system, somewhat parallel to the perceptual and cognitive processing hierarchies, elicits emotional responses to music.

The processing of music requires attention, externally directed attention required for hearing, internally directed attention required for comprehension and imagination. In this paper we have, among other things, explored the effects of exposure to musical stimuli on the attention of a test subject using electroencephalography or EEG. The results may be modest, but they are certainly encouraging. The study of how the brain processes music is relevant not only for this specific field of interest, but also for the whole of neuroscience.

We have tried to capture or summarize what we have learned about how the brain processes music in a concept map, or rather the beginning of a concept map, for the neuroscience of music and the brain. The concept map was made using [Cytoscape](#) software.

General discussion

Lessons learned

We have aimed for a cross-domain or cross-subject paper, which has a biology part but also a physics part and an introductory part in music and music theory. We have chosen a broad approach also because at the onset of our study it was still uncertain whether we would be able to make EEG recordings ourselves or not, something we really wanted to do in the biology part of our study - it being the only way to make measurements of brain activity ourselves that might be within reach. This broad subject area turned out to be a vast area of multidisciplinary science. It was hard at times to keep the scope of our paper within feasible limits. We've had to reconsider and redefine the scope and focus several times. Once we had an EEG device and EEG analysis software at our disposal and working, we chose to further focus on the neurobiology part of our study. We learned that is important to make a sound assessment of the feasibility of a research idea beforehand and also that it is important to be able to adjust your plan to changing insights and new opportunities.

It was hard to find the appropriate statistical test for our data of the final chapter. Statistical tests are covered only to a limited extent in the Wiskunde B and Wiskunde D curriculum. We checked the appropriateness of the paired Student's t-test with our tutor for this paper. It is important to choose the appropriate test to get valid answers.

What lies ahead

What lies ahead in the study of music and the brain? The study of how the brain processes music has shown to be relevant not only for the understanding of this specific topic but also for the understanding of how the brain works in general. What lies ahead in the application of music in biomedical research and in clinical practice? In another area of investigation, music has proved to be beneficial for the recovery of patients and the performance of surgeons alike (Fu, V. X., Oomens, P., Merkus, N., & Jeekel, J., 2021).

What lies ahead in neuroimaging? The focus of neuroimaging research will not much longer be on the localization of function to a specific area of the brain. New techniques are being developed to trace tracts of neurons that connect networks of brain locations in order to better understand how they interact. A new technique called diffusion MRI or dMRI, is an MRI technique that maps the diffusion of water in terms of quantity and flow direction. The quantity and flow direction of diffusion of water follows tracts of neurons. It generates previously unseen images of the brain's interconnected networks.

What lies ahead in the application of brain computer interfaces in biomedical research and in clinical practice? Our modest Muse2™ EEG device is a true brain computer interface, be it the way we used it as a one directional one. The ambitions of [Neuralink](#) in the usage of brain machine interfaces are unparalleled and hold a lot of promise for the future. The [NeuroTechX](#) global community of neuroscience and neurotechnology enthusiasts helps to bring these developments within the reach of many.

Figure 68 dMRI image of tracts of neurons in a human brain (Thomas Schultz, Wikimedia Commons)

Glossary

Actin

Actin is a contractile protein found in muscle tissue, it is also present in the outer hair cells of the organ of Corti, where it renders motor properties and motility to these cells.

Amygdala

The amygdala is a brain structure, beyond the auditory pathway, part of the basal ganglia or cerebral nuclei and thus located in the telencephalon, which is part of the forebrain. The amygdala mediates emotion and motivation.

Auditory cortex

The auditory cortex is at the end of the auditory pathway, it is located on the middle temporal gyrus of the temporal lobe, it processes the auditory signals from the cochlea.

Auditory pathway

The auditory pathway is a succession of brain structures and neural tracts leading from the cochlea, via cochlear nerve, hindbrain, midbrain, and forebrain to the auditory cortex.

Broca's area

Broca's area is an area of the cerebral cortex, beyond the auditory pathway, located in the frontal lobe of the cerebral hemisphere. Broca's area enables both speech and the expression of music. Broca's area occurs most commonly in the left cerebral hemisphere.

Cadence

A cadence serves a similar purpose as a comma or a full stop in language in a sentence, it brings a melody to a rest before continuing or to a close (Winterson, 2014).

Concert pitch

Concert pitch is the pitch reference to which a group of musical instruments are tuned for a performance. The most common tuning standard uses 440 Hz for the A above the middle C as a reference note, with all other notes being set relative to it. (Wikipedia)

Chord

A chord is the simultaneous sounding of two or more notes (Winterson, 2014).

Clef

A clef is the symbol at the beginning of a staff serving as a reference for the notes shown on the staff.

Cochlear nuclei

The cochlear nuclei are brain structures, part of the auditory pathway, located in the pons, part of the metencephalon, which in turn is part of the hindbrain. The cochlear nuclei receive the auditory signals from the auditory or cochlear nerve.

Consonance

Psychologically, consonance is when two or more notes sound together with an absence of a perceived roughness. Western listeners consider intervals produced by frequency ratios such 1:2 (octave), 3:2 (fifth), or 4:3 (fourth) as consonant (Vuust, 2022).

Decibel (dB)

Unit used to compare two levels of power of a signal. Two power levels P and P_0 differ n decibel when $n = 10 \cdot \log(P/P_0)$, human audibility has an amazing range of about 1 to 10^{12} dB, one dB is about the smallest change in power the human ear can detect (Oxford Dictionary of Biology, 2015).

Dissonance

Dissonance is the antonym of consonance. Dissonances are intervals produced by frequency ratios formed from numbers greater than 4 (Vuust, 2022).

Dopamine

Dopamine is a neurotransmitter, it is the neurotransmitter released by the nucleus accumbens, part of the reward system of the brain, when listening to music thus mediating the pleasure of listening to good music.

Electrocardiography (ECG)

An electrophysiological method that measures and records electrical activity of the heart, invented by the Dutch physician Willem Einthoven in the early 20th century.

Electroencephalography (EEG)

An electrophysiological method that measures and records electrical activity of the brain, invented by the German psychiatrist Hans Berger in the early 20th century (Vuust, 2022).

Event-related potential (ERP)

A very small electrical voltage generated in brain structures in response to specific events or stimuli (Vuust, 2022).

Fast Fourier Transform

Fast Fourier transform (FFT) is an algorithm that computes the Fourier transform of a sequence or time series of observations of a measure varying in time. It is a much-used algorithm with implementations in several computer languages, for instance MATLAB and Python. Fourier analysis or Fourier transform converts a signal from the time domain to a representation in the frequency domain.

Functional MRI (fMRI)

A neuroimaging technique that images rapid changes in blood oxygenation levels and thus activity in the brain (Vuust, 2022).

Genomics

Subdivision of genetics concerned with the study of whole genomes, typically involving the nowadays highly automated generating, analyzing, and comparing of nucleotide sequences of whole genomes, at the individual or species level (Oxford Dictionary of Biology, 2015).

Glutamate

Glutamate is an amino acid and neurotransmitter, it is the most abundant excitatory neurotransmitter in the brain and also the neurotransmitter between the inner hair cells of the organ of Corti in the cochlea and the afferent fibers of the cochlear nerve.

Groove

In contemporary music, a persistently repeated pattern, played by the rhythm section. In music psychology the pleasurable sensation of wanting to move to music (Vuust, 2022).

Harmonics

In the context of music harmonics are tones with a frequency that are multiples of a base or fundamental frequency. Most natural sounds are composites of a fundamental frequency and its harmonics.

Harmonic cadences

Stereotypical patterns consisting of two or more chords that conclude a phrase, section or piece of music. They are often used to establish a sense of tonality (Vuust, 2022).

Harmony

The combination of multiple simultaneously pitched sounds to form a chord, and subsequent chord progressions, a fundamental building block of Western music (Vuust, 2022)

Hippocampus

The hippocampus is a brain structure, beyond the auditory pathway, part of the telencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain. The hippocampus produces and retrieves memories, is involved in learning, and regulates emotional responses.

Hypothalamus

The hypothalamus is a brain structure, beyond the auditory pathway, located under the thalamus, which is part of the diencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain. The hypothalamus is the center of homeostasis and connects the endocrine system to the nervous system. It plays a role in autonomic arousal following external stimuli including music.

Immunohistochemistry

Immunohistochemistry is an application of immunostaining. It involves the process of selectively identifying antigens in cells of a tissue section, with antibodies binding specifically to the antigens of interest (Wikipedia).

Inferior colliculus

The inferior colliculus is a brain structure, part of the auditory pathway, located in the mesencephalon or midbrain.

Independent Component Analysis

Independent Component Analysis (ICA) is a signal processing method used to separate independent signal sources in a recording of signals by multiple sensors. For instance, when recording an electroencephalogram (EEG), ICA can separate out artifacts embedded in the data, since they are usually independent of each other (Delorme, 2020).

Inner hair cells

The inner hair cells, innervated by afferent fibers to the brain stem, are the sensory cells of the organ of Corti responsible for signal transduction (Luo, 2019).

Interval

In the context of music an interval is the distance between two notes, intervals are measured by the total number of notes its spans including start and end note (Winterson, 2015).

Key signature

The key signature indicates in which particular scale a piece of music is played. A key signature is positioned at the beginning of every line of music, after the clef, before the time signature (Winterson, 2015).

Lateral lemniscus

The lateral lemniscus is a brain structure, part of the auditory pathway, located in the rhombencephalon or hindbrain.

Medial geniculate nuclei

The medial geniculate nuclei are brain structures, part of the auditory pathway, located in the thalamus, which is part of the diencephalon, which in turn is part of the forebrain.

Melody

Patterns of pitches of sounds unfolding over time, following cultural conventions (Vuust, 2022).

Metre

A framework governing the interpretation of regular recurring patterns and accents in rhythm (Vuust, 2022).

Neural network

In biology a neural network is an ensemble of interconnected neurons that act together to perform a specific function (Luo, 2019). In computing a (artificial) neural network is an information processing model inspired by biological neural networks used to solve complex computational problems (Vuust, 2014, 2022).

Nucleus accumbens

The nucleus accumbens is a brain structure, beyond the auditor pathway, part of the basal ganglia or cerebral nuclei located in each hemisphere and is part of the reward system of the brain. The nucleus accumbens releases the neurotransmitter dopamine when listening to music.

Outer hair cells

The outer hair cells of the organ of Corti, innervated by efferent fibers from the brain stem, through their motor properties, amplify and modulate signal transduction by the inner hair cells (Luo, 2019).

Pitch

The perceptual correlate of frequency in sounds, that allows their ordering on a frequency-related musical scale (Vuust, 2022).

Power Spectral Density

The Power Spectral Density (PSD) is a measure of the intensity of a time-varying signal distributed in the frequency domain, expressed as V^2/Hz . It differs from the measure Power Spectrum, which is the intensity of a frequency band of a time-varying signal distributed in the frequency domain, expressed as V^2 .

Predictive Coding of Music (PCM)

The PCM model describes the coherent processes of perception, action, emotion and learning when listening to music, following a probabilistic approach, applicable to studies of Western music. (Vuust, 2014, 2022)

Prestin

A protein that mediates electromotility in the outer hair cells of the organ of Corti in the cochlea (Luo, 2019).

Reticular formation

The reticular formation is a brain structure, beyond the auditory pathway, located in the mesencephalon or midbrain, it is a network of neurons involved in alertness and attention.

Perception

Perception is the conscious perceiving of sensed stimuli – not all sensed stimuli are consciously perceived (Mason, 2019).

Putamen

The putamen is a brain structure, beyond the auditory pathway, a component of the basal ganglia, part of the telencephalon and forebrain. It processes rhythm and coordinates body movement.

Rhythm

The temporal sequence that organizes sounds, and the pauses between them, into a repeatable pattern (Tamsiea, 2021). The structured arrangement of successive sound events over time, a primary parameter of musical structure. Rhythm perception is based on the perception of duration and grouping of these events and can be seen achieved even if sounds are not discrete, such as amplitude modulated sounds (Vuust, 2022).

Scale

A scale is a pattern of related pitches, that is used to create melody (Winterson, 2015).

Statistical learning

The ability of the brain to extract statistical regularities from the world outside to learn about its environment (Vuust, 2022).

Stereocilia

Short usually non-motile hairlike structures which form an array on the apical surface of sensory hair cells (Oxford Dictionary of Biology, 2015).

Superior olivary nuclei

The superior olivary nuclei are brain structures, part of the auditory pathway, located in the pons, part of the metencephalon, which in turn is part of the hindbrain.

Timbre

Also known as tone color or tone quality, the perceived quality of a sound, including its spectral composition (Vuust, 2022).

Time signature

The time signature indicates the number of beats in each bar and the note-value of the beat. The time signature is positioned at the beginning of the first line of music only, after the key signature (Winterson, 2015).

Tone

A tone is a measure of pitch in music and music theory.

Tonality

In Western music, the organization of melody and harmony in a hierarchy of relations, often pointing towards a central pitch, the tonal centre or the tonic (Vuust, 2022).

Transcriptome

A snapshot of the expression pattern of genes in a cell, including the types and the relative abundance of the different mRNA transcripts present in the cell (Oxford Dictionary of Biology, 2015).

Weber's law

The perceived magnitude of a stimulus equals the proportion of the intensity of the stimulus of the intensity of the whole of similar stimuli in the background (Mason, 2019).

Wernicke's area

Wernicke's area is an area of the cerebral cortex, beyond the auditory pathway, located in the temporal lobe and enables the comprehension of spoken and written language as well as comprehension of music. Wernicke's area occurs most commonly in the left cerebral hemisphere.

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Attachments³

Lab notebook
Raw data
Source code

³ Attachments are separate documents. Raw data published at
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7605576>